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ICT Standardisation Observatory and Support Facility in Europe

D3.3 Fellowship Programme Interim Report

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Authors	Mona Marill (AUS)
Reviewers	Astor Nummelin Carlberg (OFE), Maria Giuffrida (Trust-IT)

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EU-CON	Classified Information: CONFIDENTIEL UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	
EU-SEC	EU-SEC. Classified Information: SECRET UE (Commission Decision 2005/444/EC)	

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DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

StandICT.eu 2026 is a coordination and support action co-funded by European Commission to foster the European experts' engagement in international ICT standardisation. StandICT.eu 2026 focuses on horizontal and vertical ICT fields that crucial for the European Digital Single Market and that are defined in the Rolling Plan for ICT Standardisation¹. This three-year project kick-off in January 2023, running until the end of December 2025. Its main objective is three-fold; firstly, it runs a **Fellowship Programme** offering direct financial support to 300+ fellows for their work in ICT standardisation working groups and technical committees. The series of 9 open calls reserves a total budget of 2,925K€ for direct funding. Secondly, it **operates the European Observatory for ICT Standardisation (EUOS)** that is one-stop-shop for European ICT experts including an up-to-date standards repository as well as technical working groups sharing insights about ongoing ICT standardisation efforts across different standards bodies and related initiatives. Thirdly, it runs the **Academy** providing training material for future European experts in ICT standardisation.

The StandICT.eu consortium gathers six partners experienced in European projects, ICT standardisation and ecosystem building. These partner include: **Dublin City University** (IE) - Financial and Administrative Coordinator, **Trust-IT Srl** (IT) - Technical Coordinator, **OpenForum Europe** (BE), **AUSTRALO Marketing Lab** (ES), **European Digital SME Alliance** (BE), and **Fraunhofer Institute for Systems and Innovation Research ISI** (DE).

This deliverable focuses on StandICT.eu 2026 efforts in the Work Package 3 “*Management facility for EU experts in ICT standardisation*” “The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme”, and task 3.2 “*StandICT.eu fellowship programme: monitoring & impact reports of successful applicants*”. It reports the methodologies and first results achieved in the StandICT.eu Fellowship programme.

The success StandICT.eu 2026 Programme is directly dependent on the effective management and monitoring of the contracted fellowships. The management of the Open Calls, the evaluation of the received applications and the contracting of evaluators is overseen

¹ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2024>

by TRUST-IT, and as a complementary action to this, AUSTRALO manages the implementation of an effective monitoring and impact assessment strategies. On one hand, the continuous monitoring of the fellowships helps to follow up closely the fellows' project deployment and progress making sure that the contracted work plans are respected. On the other hand, the impact assessment enables to analyse the impact of the fellowship programme to the European and International standardisation landscapes, on both individual and global levels.

As of, M17, in total 107 fellows were selected for funding and monitored in the programme representing a total of **979.841K€ of allocated direct funding**. The continuous monitoring of these fellowship includes regular direct communication with the funded fellows to ensure that the fellowships run according to the initial plans as well as monitoring and validation of the submitted fellowship reports. **This monitoring assesses the fellowships in terms of achieved contributions to the international ICT standardisation and their potential impact for relevant stakeholders**. Also, as a part of the monitoring process, the StandICT.eu team has established an **“Early Warning System”** triggering alerts from the funded experts to the European Commission if any observed ongoing standardisation efforts go against the European policies, values, and regulations.

In addition, the impact of the Fellowship projects was timely and continuously communicated to the StandICT.eu community throughout the project, to leverage the synergies among the funded projects and running related standardisation efforts. For this purpose, **a series of 9 Impact Reports was started**, with an edition dedicated to each open call, gathering the fellowship stories of the funded experts. Open Call 1 Impact report was released in March 2024 and the second edition in May 2024, the next publications of the series will follow the established editorial plan.

Until Open Call 3, **12 different SDOs or standards bodies have benefitted from the fellowship projects** in various horizontal and vertical technology areas including artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, quantum technologies, 5G/6G, E-Identification and E-Privacy, as the most funded sectors. In average, **65% of the funded fellowship contribution to the work of international standardisation organisations (SDOs)**, including, ISO, ISO/IEC, IEEE, ITU, IETF etc. Furthermore, **69 direct contributions to developing new or revising existing standards have been tackled by the work of our funded fellows**.

The Fellowship Programme is running strong with an average of one hundred applications for each open call. Therefore, the StandICT.eu 2026 expects to witness growing impact of the programme during the second half of the project.

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ABBREVIATIONS

ACRONYM	Explanation
AUS	Australo Interinnov Marketing Lab SL (Project Partner)
DCU	Dublin City University (Financial coordinator)
DMS	Document Management System (Project Partner)
DSME	European Digital SME Alliance
EAG	External Advisory Group
EC	European Commission
EPE	External Pool of Evaluators
ESO	European Standardisation Organisation
EUOS	European Observatory for ICT Standardisation
FHG	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft (Project Partner)
FOREST	Forum on European Strategy for ICT Standards
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
NSB	National Standardisation Body
OC	Open Call
OFE	Open Forum Europe (Project Partner)
PC	Project Coordinator
PMB	Project Management Board
SDO	International Standardisation Organisation
TC	Technical Committee
TL	Task Leader
TRUST-IT	Trust-IT Srl (Administrative Technical coordinator)
TWG	Technical Working Group
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package
SDO	International Standardisation Organisation

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This report summarises the first results and impact of the Fellowship Programme on the International ICT Standardisation Landscape, and its main objectives are to:

- Explain the used monitoring and impact assessment strategies.
- Provide an overview of the monitoring status from the project's first half, from January 2023 until May 2024 (M1-M18).
- Share the fellowship outcomes on a global level, impacting the different SDOs, WGs and TCs but also the engaged stakeholders.
- Promote the Individual Impact Reports gathering the fellows' success stories for each Open Call Batch.
- Share lessons learnt and set the plan for the next steps in the impact assessment until the end of the project.

1.2 Structure

The document consists of the following sections:

- **Section 2** details the overall monitoring framework of the Fellowship Program implemented as a continuum of StandICT.eu 2023 Programme. It describes the used monitoring methodology and tools as well as it provides an overview of monitored fellowships from Batch 1 (OC1) until Batch 4 (OC4).
- **Section 3** is dedicated to the impact assessment of the fellowship programme from the global standpoint providing insights to how the funded fellowships have contributed concretely to the international ICT standardisation landscape.
- **Section 4** helps to understand the fellowship programme impact with individual success stories that are published in a series of individual impact reports for each open call batch. This section explains the approach of the impact dissemination from the perspective of the individual fellowships.
- **Section** [Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.](#) offers the conclusion of task 3.3 including the lessons learnt and recommendations for the next steps in conducting the task.

1.3 Relation with other project deliverables

The following project outcomes correlate with this task:

In **WP1 “Project Management and Coordination”**, one report can be linked to the present report.

- D1.2 DMP – Data Management Plan (Fraunhofer, M1)

In WP3 “The StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme” the four monitoring reports provide detailed information about each Open Calls’ main results and findings, the evaluation and fellowship contracting processes:

- D3.1 Call monitoring report no1 (Call 1& Call 2) (Trust-IT, M11)
- D3.2 Call monitoring report no2 (Call 3 & Call 4) (Trust-IT, M19)
- D3.4 Call monitoring report no3 (remaining calls) (Trust-IT, M30)

Also, the present report will have a second iteration at the end of the project:

- D3.5 Final fellowship programme report (AUS, M35)

WP5 “Engagement & Synergies”, grow, expands, and animates the StandICT.eu’s stakeholders’ community. One related output, with two iterations, from this WP are relevant to the task 3.3:

- D5.1 / 5.2 Stakeholder engagement mid-term / final report (M17 / M35, DSME)

WP6 “Dissemination, promotion, communication, and sustainability” contributes to promote the open calls and to dissemination the funded fellowships. Here, five reports can be linked to results from the StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme monitoring.

- D6.1 Plan for communication & stakeholder engagement strategy & plan and promotion of the open call (M3, Trust-IT)
- D6.2 Sustainability strategy (M18, Trust-IT)
- D6.3 Policy Recommendations (M12, DCU)
- D6.5 Policy engagement strategy (M36, DCU)
- D6.6 Proposed Sustainability Framework (M36, Trust-IT)

2. MONITORING FRAMEWORK

StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme has built its monitoring framework on the solid basis created during the past editions of the program (StandICT.eu 2018 and StandICT.eu 2023), with the aim to keep the monitoring process well-structured, but flexible and adjustable according to the needs raising from the other StandICT.eu 2026 activities. AUS leads the monitoring under WP3 “StandICT.eu Fellowship Programme”, task 3.2 “Monitoring and impact reports of successful applicants”, with continuous support from Trust-IT, managing the Trust-Grants application platform and evaluation process, and DCU, in charge of processing the grant payments.

The aim of the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme is to act as a fully functional funding mechanism, adapting an end-user-friendly design and operating in a well-defined framework. Therefore, the operational monitoring framework is crucial for its success. It enables to evaluate the achievements of each funded fellowship based on their defined work plans, disseminate the achieved fellowship results and impact. This way, the programme ensures to give the best value for the public funding invested.

Once the evaluation of the Open Call applications by the external pool of evaluators (EPE) is finalised, the selected fellows are informed of their successful application and the fellowship activities can take place as planned in the application. Each Fellowship Program Batch (from 1 to 9, corresponding to each Open Call) is monitored in a defined framework.

FIGURE 1 MONITORING STRATEGY

As shown in Figure 1, the Fellowship Programme Monitoring framework consists of two approaches:

Firstly, **monitoring** covers the collection, communication, and use of information about the progress of each funded fellowship. With a weekly routine, the StandICT.eu team makes sure that all contracted projects are running as planned, respecting the set goals and timeline. In case challenges or problems (for instance, with the project delivery date) the responsible staff members solve the problem with the concerned fellow. Moreover, the monitoring enables to make sure that the entire fellowship programme is executed according to the plan with respect of the set timelines and tangible results.

Secondly, **the Impact assessment** analyses the collected monitoring information and producing communication material, such as infographics, templates for social media posts, and public impact reports, disseminating the fellowship programme outcomes to all stakeholders. The impact assessment runs on two levels: on the individual level including fellowship success stories and, on the programme-wide level highlighting the global impact of the fellowship programme on the international ICT standardisation ecosystem. The impact assessment gives a special attention to the following indicators of impacts of the fellowships:

- Covered ICT Sector, engaged SDO and Working Groups (WG)/ Technical Committees (TC).
- Role of the funded fellows (chairs, convenors, co-chair, co-convenors etc.).
- Direct contribution to new / revised standards.
- Participation in newly established WGs / TCs.
- Contribution in specific deliverables.
- Relation to other research and innovation projects (e.g., H2020, Horizon Europe, DEP).
- Forecasted impact of the contribution on the EU SMEs and on the society.
- Recommendations for the necessary further standardisation actions in the concerned areas.
- Contribution to the EUOS technical work groups' efforts.
- Early warning of standardisation practices going against European values, policies or regulations.

The impact assessment benefits the entire StandICT.eu stakeholders' community, and especially the involved experts and policy makers, notably from the European Commission, the Multi Stakeholder Platform on ICT Standardisation, and High-Level Forum for ICT Standardisation, enabling to understand better the ongoing standardisation priorities within the different SDOs and anticipate the needs in further standardisation.

2.1 Monitoring Methodology and Tools

All funded fellowships are monitored throughout their duration, from the start date until the ending date, which are defined in the fellowship application and confirmed upon the selection of the fellowship. During this continuous monitoring, overseen by AUS, the following project aspects are controlled:

- Identification of successes and problems during the fellowship implementation.
- Informed and timely decision making by project manager to support the implementation.

- Accountability for the activity and results achieved.
- Fellows' contribution to the dissemination of the results and participation in the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme.
- Assessment and validation of the fellowship's achievements and activities.

Figure 2 shows the StandICT.eu partners role in the monitoring process and steps that each fellowship monitoring process follows.

Steps for the Fellowship Monitoring

FIGURE 2 MONITORING STEPS

Moreover, the monitoring milestones vary according to the fellowship type, as described in Table 1; long-term fellowships submit two monitoring reports (interim and final) whereas short-term and one-short fellowships submit only the final report at the end of their activity.

TABLE 1 FELLOWSHIP TYPES

Fellowship Type	Max. duration and funding	Description	Monitoring milestones
Long-Term (LT) Fellowship	Up to 6 months and 10K€	Contribution to ongoing standards development as a chair, convener, rapporteur, or member of an SDO WG. E.g. comments on standards development and drafts, attending meetings also as an observer, paying membership fees.	Interim report (in M3). Final report (in M6).
Short-term (ST) Fellowship	Up to 3 months and 5K€	Contribution to standards documentation e.g. liaison to WG, comments on standards drafts, participation at meeting paying membership or registration fees.	Final report (in M3).
One-short (OS) Fellowship	Up to 3 months and 3K€	Support to ensure participation at workshop or event (e.g., participant, observer, presentation).	Final report (in M3).

Next to the defined process, a set of tools and methods support the successful implementation of the monitoring plan, these include the fellowship reporting templates submitted via TRUST-GRANTS™ platform², and continuous communication with the funded fellows, which are described in the next sub-sections.

2.1.1 Reporting and TRUST-GRANTS™ Platform

The TRUST-GRANTS™ platform enables monitoring of the fellowships progress in real time based on the start and end dates of each individual funded fellowship, as well as on the work plan provided as a part of the fellowship application. The project team consults the platform daily to identify new achieved fellowship milestones (namely, interim, and final report submissions) and possible deviations. Only the designated StandICT.eu team members are granted rights to access the project monitoring tool on the platform. On the other hand, all fellows access their personal dashboards on this platform to submit, which their fellowship reports and to check the progress of their fellowship status (i.e., in evaluation, not accepted, approved, validated, in payment, withdrawn, or not eligible).

² <https://grants2026.standict.eu/>

ID	Title	Username	Name	Surname	Report Status	Report details
01-117	Support as Secretary for ETSI ISG SAI	acadzow	Alex	Cadzow	✓ On Track	Report Details
01-180	Standards for information security and cloud service providers	Karim Tobich	Karim	Tobich	✓ On Track	Report Details
01-212	Artificial Intelligence – Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations	Bonde V	Viveka	Bonde	✓ On Track	Report Details
01-222	Leading the development of ITU standards for IoT applications in smart cities and communities	mangelopoulos	Marios	Angelopoulos	! Delay	Report Details
01-228	IRTF NMRG agenda refinement for assessing and reducing the environmental impact of networking	jerome francois	Jérôme	Francois	✓ On Track	Report Details
01-285	Philosophical Contributions on TS6254 - Explainability	carloszednik	Carlos	Zednik	! Delay	Report Details

FIGURE 3 TRUST-GRANTS PLATFORM FOR MONITORING

The fellows perform their all reporting via TRUST-GRANTS™ respecting the set deadlines (at the mid-term and/or at the end of their fellowship, depending on their project type). This platform is a one-stop-shop for the fellows, where they manage both the applications to StandICT.eu Open Calls and the reporting of the retained fellowships.

The templates of both reports follow the same structure: Section 1 gathers questions enabling to draft the profile of the funded expert and their background in ICT standardisation, Section 2 is dedicated to the funded fellowship activity, its tangible results and foreseen impact in the ICT standardisation arena.

Interim Report, that LT fellows submit at their project M3, enable to follow the mid-term progress of the fellowships monitoring namely: the concerned standardisation challenges and gaps, the addressed SDOs, WGs and TCs, the number of participated meetings, webinars, workshops as well as the overall progress compared to the initial work plan. See *Annex 1 – StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Interim Report Template*.

Final Report, submitted at the end of all funded fellowships (at M3 or M6 based on the fellowship type), contain questions notably regarding the achieved standardisation activities but also on the project's contribution to the new / revised standards and technical working groups, impact on SMEs, on the society as well as the possible contributions to the EUOS Technical Working Groups (TWGs). See *Annex 2: StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Final Report Template*

The project managers review the content and the quality of all submitted reports, and if the set activity objectives are well in process (in interim reports) or were met (in final reports). We also examine that the quality criteria are met, the reports are validated enabling the project to move towards the next milestone. These quality criteria concern to assess the consistency of responses in the open questions; if all questions are addressed, and if the data provided enables to understand the main achievements and to draft the fellowship story of the fellowship for disseminating the project impact.

Upon the validation of submitted final report, DCU team is notified, and they launch the grant payment process. In case that the submitted reports do not meet the set quality criteria, the re-submission of the report is requested with information on the improvements to be done for the validation of the fellowship.

2.1.2 Communication

To raise awareness about the monitoring process, the achieved fellowships, and their impact to the community, StandICT.eu 2026 team run internal and external communication.

Regarding the **internal communication** with the funded fellows, AUS is in regular contact via emails with the funded fellows making sure that the fellows are aware of the available reporting process, tools, and the set deadlines. In case of delays or other foreseen complications during the fellowship, AUS connects the fellow with TRUST-IT team to mitigate all risks impacting the project as quickly as possible.

The external communication related to the monitoring focuses on the impact assessment and dissemination towards the StandICT.eu 2026 community. It includes a series of fellowship impact reports as well as regular communication on StandICT.eu communication channels, on LinkedIn (see Figure 4) and X (see Figure 5).

FIGURE 4 EXAMPLE OF LINKEDIN POST OF A FUNDED FELLOWSHIP

FIGURE 5 EXAMPLE OF A POST ABOUT THE FUNDED FELLOWSHIPS ON X

In addition, we share the profiles of the funded fellows via a dedicated page on the StandICT.eu 2026 website³.

FIGURE 6 FUNDED FELLOWS PAGE ON THE STANDICT.EU WEBSITE

³ <https://www.standict.eu/funded-fellows>

2.1.3 Early Warning System

During the kick-off meeting of StandICT.eu 2026 (hosted in Pisa, Italy, in February 2023), the project officers from the European Commission requested the project to set up an early warning system helping to alert the EC officials in case the funded fellows or the engaged experts identify any ongoing standardisation process that goes against the European policies, values or regulations. To meet this request, the partners added a specific question in the fellowship application forms and final report templates:

TABLE 2 MONITORING FOR EARLY WARNING SYSTEM

Monitoring question for early warning system	Response options
StandICT.eu serves the EU interests in the international ICT standardisation scene and reports directly to the European Commission. As a part of your standardisation activities, have you observed any draft standards being processed that are against the European values, policies, or regulation? <i>Please note that this information will be kept entirely anonymous and shared confidentially only with the European Commission.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Yes - No / If yes, please elaborate your response.

These responses are collected as a part of the monitoring process, and reported anonymously to the consortium members who contribute to the FOREST group (running under StandICT.eu 2026) to further analyse collected early warnings in the different ICT sectors, and provide the aggregated data, observations, and possible recommendations to the EC.

2.2 Monitored Fellows Until M17

Around the mid-term of the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme, in May 2024 as this report was in writing, 107 fellowships have been funded until open call 3. As highlighted in Figure 7, the majority (101) of these funded fellowships were long-term activities, running up to six months, whereas seven were short-term projects, running up to three months.

17% of the funded experts were women, which holds on to the gender gap in the ICT and STEM areas that are represented by a strong majority of male professionals; 18% of ICT professionals are women⁴. Furthermore, and even more the ICT standardisation space which historically is very male. Finally, **57% of the funded fellows work for SMEs or for IT Consultancy / Development**.

The funded applications cover **a wide spectrum of horizontal and vertical ICT sectors**, with artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, network and information security, quantum technologies and electronic identification among the most popular funded ICT topics. Moreover, **65% of the funded fellowships contribute primarily to international standardisation organisations (SDOs)**, including, ISO/IEC, ISO, ITU, IEEE, IETF, and IEC, whereas the reminder work for European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering CEN, CEN/CENELEC and ETSI, and other standardisation bodies as O-RAN and 3DPP.

⁴ www.eppgroup.eu/what-we-do/with-eu-countries/ireland/europe-needs-more-women-in-stem

FIGURE 7 OVERVIEW OF THE FUNDED FELLOWSHIPS OC1 - OC3

The annually updated **rolling plan for ICT standardisation**⁵ guides the eligible topics for the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme’s open calls, and the funded fellowships focus on the selected ICT areas from four priority areas:

- **Foundational drivers** (including Data Economy, Cybersecurity/Network and Information security, and E-Privacy).
- **Key enablers and security** (including 5G and Beyond (6G), Cloud and Edge Computing, Big Data & Open data, Internet of Things (IoT), Electronic identification and trust services (including e-signature), E-infrastructure for data and computing intensive service, Broadband infrastructure mapping, Accessibility of ICT products and services, Artificial Intelligence, European Global Navigation Satellite Systems (EGNSS), and Quantum Technologies).
- **Sustainable Growth** (including Smart Grids and Smart Metering, Smart and Sustainable Cities, ICT Environmental impact, European Electronic Toll Service (EETS), Intelligent Transport Systems, Digitisation of European Industry, Robotics and

⁵ <https://joinup.ec.europa.eu/collection/rolling-plan-ict-standardisation/rolling-plan-2024>

autonomous systems, Construction building information modelling, Common information sharing environment (CISE) for the EU Maritime domain, Water management digitalisation, Single European Sky, U-Space, Circular Economy including Digital Product Passport).

- **Innovation for Digital Single Market** (including E-Procurement, E-Invoicing, Retail payments, Preservation of digital cinema, FinTech & RegTech Standardisation, Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, Metaverse including Citiverse).
- **Societal challenges** (including E-Health, Healthy living and ageing, Digital skills, Digital learning, E-Government, E-call, Pandemic Preparedness, Safety, transparency and due process online, Emergency communications and public warning systems).

Figure 8 highlights the most targeted ICT areas by ICT standardisation rolling plan categories. Foundational divers as well as key enablers and security remain the most popular topics, with 79 funded applications, followed by ICT areas for sustainable growth, with 15 funded fellowships.

FIGURE 8 OC1- OC3 FELLOWSHIPS BY ICT STANDARDISATION ROLLING PLAN

2.2.1 Batch 1 – Open Call #1

The first StandICT.eu 2026 Open Call⁶ was launched on the 9th of May 2023 and closed on the 10th of July 2023. It received 105 applications out of which **35 were selected for funding**, with an overall **321,000 Euro granted**. Once more, this open call confirmed the excellent quality of most of the submitted proposals, marking a noticeably high average quality score (the average score of submitted applications was 7,74 and that of funded applications was 8,9 in a 1 to 10 scoring scale).

The funded applications provided an extensive geographical coverage with **16 different EU or associated countries** (with most representants from Belgium). Moreover, **17% of the funded experts were female**. **30% of the fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme**, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship or fellowships in the previous programme (under StandICT.eu 2023).

The retained fellowships represented with a balance across the key technologies, and with a wide spectrum of SDOs that benefit from the competence and expertise of the fellows. As outlined in Figure 9 , major part of the granted fellows has chosen their focus across a varied range of horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular areas in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, quantum technologies as well as network and information security. This funding batch is marked by a great variety of vertical ICT areas covered by the fellowships, namely metaverse and digital product passport that were the targeted areas of the announced call.

62% of the fellows' activity contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, namely in ISO, IEC, ISO/IEC, ITU, IEEE, IETF, while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), namely in ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC, and another group engaged in standardisation (namely, O-RAN).

⁶ <https://www.standict.eu/standicteu-2026-1st-open-call>

1st Open Call
APPLICATIONS FUNDED

FIGURE 9 OVERVIEW OF RETAINED FELLOWSHIPS UNDER OC1

Annex 3 provides the complete list of the funded fellowships under StandICT.eu 2026 Open Call #1. In addition, more information of their fellowship contributions can be found on “Following the fellows – Impact Report 1” (see Section 4.1.1).

2.2.2 Batch 2 - Open Call #2

The second StandICT.eu 2026 Open Call⁷ was launched on the 31st of July 2023 and closed on the 2nd of October 2023. It totalled 83 eligible applications received out of which **37 were selected for funding, with an overall 326,000 Euro granted**. It also confirmed the excellent quality of most of the submitted proposals, marking a noticeably high average quality score (the minimum threshold to access funding was 7,96 score in a 1 to 10 scoring scale).

The funded applications provided extensive geographical coverage with **12 different EU or associated countries** (including five experts from the UK). Five funded experts were new to the StandICT.eu programme, and the remainder were returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship or fellowships in the previous programme (under StandICT.eu 2026 and /or 2023 Programmes).

⁷ <https://www.standict.eu/standicteu-2026-2nd-open-call>

The retained fellowships are represented with a satisfying balance across the key technologies, and with a wide spectrum of SDOs that will benefit from the competence and expertise of the applicants. As outlined in Figure 10, a major part of the granted fellows has chosen their focus across a varied range of horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular areas in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, network and information security, and quantum technologies. This funding batch is marked by a great variety of vertical ICT areas covered by the fellowships, namely circular economy and digital product passport that were especially encouraged topics in this call.

62% of the fellows’ activity contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, including IEC, IEEE, IETF, ISO, ISO/IEC and ITU, while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), covering ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC.

FIGURE 10 OVERVIEW OF RETAINED FELLOWSHIPS UNDER OC2

Annex 4 provides the complete list of the funded fellowships under StandICT.eu 2026 Open Call #2. Also, more information of their fellowship contributions can be found on “Following the fellows – Impact Report 2” (see section 4.1.2).

2.2.3 Batch 3 - Open Call #3

The third open call was running from the 30th of November 2023 until the 9th of January 2024. It received 115 applications out of which **35 were selected for funding**, with an overall **322,158 Euro granted**.

The funded applications offer a large geographic spectrum with **11 different EU or associated countries** (with most experts from Belgium, France, Italy, and Austria). **23% of the funded experts were female**. **34% of the fellows are new to the StandICT.eu programme**, and the remainder are returning fellows who have already benefited from a funded StandICT.eu fellowship or fellowships in the previous programme (under StandICT.eu 2023).

The retained fellowships represented with a satisfying balance across the key technologies, and with a wide spectrum of SDOs that will benefit of the competence and expertise of the applicants. As outlined in Figure 11, major part of the granted fellows has chosen their focus across a varied range of horizontal and vertical ICT areas; the most popular areas in this batch include artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, electronic identification as well as internet of things. Moreover, this funding batch is marked by a great variety of vertical ICT areas covered by the fellowships, namely metaverse that were the targeted areas of the announced call.

71% of the fellows' activity contribute to the activities of Committees or Working Groups operating in global SDOs, namely in ISO, IEC, ISO/IEC, ITU, IEEE, IETF, while the remainder works with European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), namely in ETSI, CEN, CEN/CENELEC, and another group engaged in standardisation (namely, O-RAN).

FIGURE 11 OVERVIEW OF RETAINED FELLOWSHIPS UNDER OC3

Annex 6 provides **the complete list of the funded fellowships under StandICT.eu 2026 Open Call #3**. More information of their fellowship contributions will be found on “Following the fellows – Impact Report 3” that will be published during Summer 2024.

2.2.4 Batch 4 - Open Call #4

The fourth open call was running from the 12th of February until the 12th of April 2024. It received 104 applications. As of authoring the report, the selection process of the funded fellowships was about to be concluded. The monitoring of this batch starts in June 2024 (M18).

3. GLOBAL FOOTPRINT OF THE FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME AT M17

This section shares the key insights about **the global impact of the funded fellowships on the international ICT standardisation landscape** (the presented data covers funded fellowships from Open Call 1 to Open Call 3 unless it is differently specified). All funded fellowships of the StandICT.eu 2026 Programme **contribute to a varied range of Standardisation organisations and bodies, and to their specific work groups (WGs) and technical committee (TCs)**. The annually updated rolling plan for ICT standardisation, coordinated by the European Commission, frames the focus and the eligible ICT areas, as mentioned in Section 2.2.

Figure 12 gives a quick overview of the initial impact that the funded fellowships have to the international ICT standardisation fora. This figure aims to reflect the general tendency of the funded fellowships; however, it is important to understand that these numbers will evolve as all running fellowships are concluded.

FIGURE 12 FACTS ABOUT THE INITIAL IMPACT OF THE FELLOWSHIP PROGRAMME

3.1 Contributions within SDOs and Standards Bodies

This section shares insights from the global impact of the fellowship programme within the SDOs benefitting from the funded fellowships. The funded fellowship contributes to the work

of different standardisation bodies developing new standards, revising obsolete ones, or disseminating existing standards towards the different stakeholders. A part of the funded experts has a key role in the standardisation committees, acting as a chairs/co-chairs, conveners/co-conveners, secretaries, moderators, and all funded act as contributing

3.1.1 Overview of the covered SDOs and Standards Bodies

65% of the funded fellowships contribute to the work of international standardisation organisations (SDOs). As shown in Table 3, ISO/IECs scores most funded fellowships among the SDOs, followed by ISO, IEEE, ITU, IEC and IETF. Among the European Standardisation Organisations (ESOs), CEN/CENELEC benefits from 20 funded fellowships, followed by CEN and ETSI. Finally, the other funded standardisation bodies include EITCI, 3-GPP, and ORAN.

TABLE 3 FELLOWSHIP CONTRIBUTIONS TO STANDARDISATION ORGANISATIONS

Standardisation Organisation	Funded fellowships benefitting the Organisation (up to OC3)	
SDOs		
	ISO/ IEC www.iso.org/Organisation/70.html	32 Funded fellowships
	ISO www.iso.org	11 Funded fellowships
	IEEE www.ieee.org	8 Funded fellowships
	ITU www.itu.int	7 Funded fellowships
	IEC www.iec.ch/homepage	5 Funded fellowships
	IETF www.ietf.org	4 Funded fellowships
ESOs		
	CEN-CENELEC www.cencenelec.eu	20 Funded fellowships

	CEN www.cencenelec.eu/about-cen	10 Funded fellowships
	ETSI www.etsi.org	7 Funded fellowships
Other Standards Bodies		
	EITCI https://eitci.org/	2 Funded fellowships
	3GPP www.3gpp.org	1 Funded fellowship
	O-RAN www.o-ran.org	1 Funded fellowship

The majority of the funded experts hold roles in several standardisation groups, and these numbers reflect their involvement in the organisation that is primarily concerned with their funded fellowship contribution.

3.1.2 Overview of the covered TCs / WGs

The StandICT.eu Programme has supported fellowships that contribute **directly to over 12 different standards organisations and over a hundred different Technical Committees and Work groups**. The fellows are engaged to work of these groups supporting them to develop new standards, revise obsolete standards and to disseminate the standardisation work across the different ecosystems and stakeholder groups.

Annex 6 – Involved Standardisation Organisations, Working Groups and Technical Committees **provides the complete list of the addressed organisations, WGs and TCs staggered by ICT sectors** (as defined in the ICT standardisation rolling plan).

3.1.3 Contributions to new and revised standards

NOTE: This subsection covers fellowship data from funding batches 1 and 2 since the data collection from the next fellowship batches was still ongoing at the time of writing.

One of the most important activities related to impact monitoring is to track the impact generated by the fellows in terms of Contribution to new/revised standards. On average, from the funding batch 1 and 2, **90% of the retained fellowships contributed to developing new standards or revising obsolete ones**. Out of the 72 fellowships (up to Open Call 2

fellowships), **54 supported the development of new standards**, and **15 fellowships worked to revise existing ones** (several fellowships contributed to both, new and revised standards).

Annex 7 List of New and Revised Standards addressed by the funded fellowships **provides the complete list of the addressed new and revised standards**, classified by ICT sector.

3.1.4 Contributions in new work groups

NOTE: This subsection covers fellowship data from funding batches 1 and 2 since the data collection from the next fellowship batches was still ongoing at the time of writing.

The funded fellowships have contributed to **15 different new working groups** across the ICT sectors. These groups are listed by ICT area on Table 4.

TABLE 4 FELLOWSHIPS' CONTRIBUTIONS TO NEW WORKING GROUPS

ICT Area	MainSDO	New Working Group
Foundational Drivers		
Network and information security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN-CENELEC JTC13 WG8 Special Working Group RED Standardisation Request CEN-CENELEC JTC13 WG9 Special Working Group on Cyber Resilience Act
Key enablers and Security		
5G & beyond 6G	ETSI IEEE	ETSI TC INT / AFI WG Working Group "Network Applications in 5G and beyond" within the IEEE Communications Society
Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC CEN/CENELEC CEN/CENELEC ISO/IEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21/WG 5 Joint Standardisation on Cybersecurity for AI systems Contributed to CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG1 and towards the establishment of a new JTC21 WG5 on Cybersecurity for AI Systems. CEN/CENELEC/JTC21/WG3 Engineering aspects ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 Artificial Intelligence, WG Trustworthiness
Quantum Technologies	CEN/CENELEC CEN/CENELEC IEC CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC22 "Quantum Technologies" Work Group 4 Quantum Communication and QKD CEN/CENELEC JTC22 Quantum Technologies ISO/IEC JTC3 - Quantum Technologies CEN/CLC JTC 22 Working Group 3 (JTC22/WG3) "Quantum Computing and Simulation"
Innovation for Digital Single Market		
Metaverse	ITU	UN ITU FG MV SG8 Sustainability, Accessibility & Inclusion
Sustainable Growth		

Robotics and autonomous systems	IEEE The TWG on Robotics. The new IEEE RAS robotic standard WG 1872.3 is in good shape and is at its first year of work. Bi-weekly meetings are underway. Two workshops at the major IEEE robotic conference (ICRA, in 2023 and 2024) were approved which is excellent. I am honoured to be the chair of the WG, where European experts are very well represented in the group of voting members. Recently a new IEEE working group was formed, based on the 1872.1, to develop a guide for the application of the robot task representation (the new 1872.1.1), that I also am a member.
Smart Grids And Smart Metering	IEC CISPR A/B/H JWG 9

3.1.5 Involvement of SDO WG / TC Chairs and Conveners

NOTE: This subsection covers fellowship data from funding batches 1 and 2 since the data collection from the next fellowship batches was still ongoing at the time of writing.

On average, **40% of the StandICT.eu fellowship experts hold a key role in the working groups or technical committees**, as a chair, co-chair, convener, or co-convener. Annex 8 – List of Funded Experts with a Key Role in a Working Group or a Technical Committee **provides a complete list of these funded experts.**

3.2 Contributions in StandICT.eu Activities

The central objective of the fellowship program is to support EU experts in their work at international standardisation organisation. In addition, **StandICT.eu aims to value the knowledge and to capitalise the know-how of the funded experts** by inviting them to contribute to the StandICT.eu 2026 activities that run along the fellowship programme.

FIGURE 13 FELLOWS' CONTRIBUTIONS TO STANDICT.EU ACTIVITIES

As shown in Figure 13, the funded and trusted experts have notably joined the external advisory group (EAG), Academy, and the EUOS technical working groups. Also, in each in-house webinar, we invite representatives from the fellowship programme to present their work. These invitations are done based on the thematic of the concerned activity, and on the expert's matching profile and expertise.

3.2.1 Contributions to the StandICT.eu expert groups

In parallel to the StandICT.eu Funding Programme, the project runs several experts' groups spurring the project's activities and ensuring that these cover the different crucial aspects of ongoing and forthcoming international ICT standardisation efforts.

The Academy⁸ provides training material for all stakeholders interested in elevating their skills in ICT standardisation. One fellow, who has been active contributor since StandICT.eu 2023 Programme is a member of this body.

The Forum for European Strategy on ICT Standards (FOREST) gathers a group of ICT standardisation experts with the goal of ensuring that the funded experts' resources are

⁸ <https://www.standict.eu/euos-training-academy>

directed to match the European Commission's goals. Its new structure and objectives were confirmed in May 2024 (M17), and two funded fellows joined the group.

The EUOS technical working groups (TWG) gather experts in specific ICT areas to develop standardisation gap analysis or landscapes⁹ that are published under StandICT.eu as public reports. Until now, **seven funded experts have actively contributed** to the efforts of these groups. Table 5 lists the different groups and the involved fellows from StandICT.eu 2026 programme.

TABLE 5 FELLOW'S CONTRIBUTIONS TO STANDICT.EU GROUPS

StandICT.eu Activity	Involved fellows
External Advisory Board	Antonio Kung (OC2)
Academy	Maria Ines Robles (OC1)
FOREST	Viveka Bonde (OC1), Christian Grafenauer (OC2)
TWG CitiVerse	Antonio Kung (OC2), Marius Preda (OC1), Kate Grant (OC2)
TWG IIOT & Edge	Alexandru Vulpe (OC1), Maria Ines Robles (OC1)

3.2.2 Contributions to the StandICT.eu webinars

In each in-house webinar, proposed by StandICT.eu to its stakeholders, we aim to provide a platform for funded fellows to participate as speakers, offering insights from their work to stakeholders in the broader ICT standardisation landscape. These fellows are invited to present in the webinar, based on their expertise on the concerned topic and their availability. Table 6 specifies the four webinars where **six funded fellows participated as speakers**.

TABLE 6 FELLOWS CONTRIBUTIONS TO THE STANDICT.EU WEBINARS

Webinar Title	Date	Contributing fellows
Women in ICT Standards #2 ¹⁰	04/07/2023	Viveka Bonde (OC1)
"Walk & Talk Webinar" - Towards the CitiVerse & a citizen-centric virtual world for EU Cities and Communities ¹¹	20/09/2023	Antonio Kung (OC2), Marius Preda (OC1), Pilar Orero (OC1)
Standards Academy Workshop: Developing leadership capacity for SMEs in European	15/11/2023	Belen Suarez (OC1)

⁹ <https://www.standict.eu/landscape-analysis-reports>

¹⁰ <https://www.standict.eu/events/webinar-women-ict-standards-focus-gender-gap-ict-standardisation-and-standards>

¹¹ <https://www.standict.eu/events/walk-talk-webinar-towards-citiverse-citizen-centric-virtual-world-eu-cities-and-communities>

and international standardisation organisations ¹²		
Women in ICT Standards #3 ¹³	07/03/2024	Sandra Feliciano (OC3)

¹² <https://www.standict.eu/meeting-standards-workshop>

¹³ <https://www.standict.eu/events/webinar-women-ict-standards-3>

4. INDIVIDUAL FELLOWSHIP STORIES UNTIL M17

The fellowship programme regularly launches new edition of its publication series “Following the Fellows” showcasing all funded fellowships under each open call batch. As of M17, two impact reports have been published, and seven more are planned. **These published reports record 1000+ views and 150+ downloads in open access**, via StandICT.eu’s open Zenodo library¹⁴.

These focus on the individual footprints of the funded fellowships enabling to showcase the results and the impact of the cascade funding programme throughout the project. Next to these reports, StandICT.eu 2026 has deployed all communication channels to share the fellowship stories, including presentations in meetings, events and webinars, newsletters, social media, and the project website.

4.1 Strategy for the Impact Reports

The series of nine reports serves the overarching objective of showcasing stories of the funded fellowships detailing the addressed standards and landscapes, how these will fill in the identified gaps as well as impact the related stakeholders and society.

The aim of the short fellowship stories is to enable the value of standardisation in creating a fair market-based competition with benefits, including better interoperability of complementary products and services, reduced costs, improved safety, and enhanced overall competition. Their critical action in protecting health, safety, security, and the environment, make standards important to the public and consumers as well. Moreover, these reports can enable stakeholders to spot gaps in ICT standards for certain technology areas and to subsequently direct recommendations for future standardisation.

Therefore, the impact reports addressed to the experts in the StandICT.eu community (e.g., experts involved in the EAG, the EUOS TWGs of the fellowship programme), but also to wider public including all targeted stakeholders of the project:

- Members in national, European, and international standards bodies.
- EU technology PPPs (such as 5GPPP, 5GAI, ECSO etc.) and associations engaged in standardisation (for instance, Digital SME Alliance, SBS, ANEC etc.).
- Large Industry Players.
- SMEs and IT consulting firms contributing to standardisation.
- Policy Makers (especially the EC, Multi Stakeholder Platform and High-Level Forum).
- Research and Innovation Projects (especially funded under the EU R&I funding programmes, and Horizon Europe).

The impact reports present the stories by different technology sectors. See here below (Figure 14) an example of a fellowship story from Belen Suarez, in Impact Report 1.

¹⁴ https://zenodo.org/communities/standict_eu/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest

Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies

Belen Suarez
Go To Innovation CEO, Reaccion Economica
Spain

Sector

Digital product passport

Engaged SDOs, WGs and TCs

CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG 2 Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and DLTs

Role

Convenor at CEN/Cenelec JTC 19 WG2
Chair of ISO TC 307 WGS

Addressed EU standardisation priorities and gaps

In my activity, I focus on tackling the gap related to blockchain and Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies as digital enabler technologies and their applications have a great potential for supporting use cases, such as future European Digital Product Passports and other use cases that could contribute positively to sustainable development and create a positive impact. At the same time, there are concerns about the environmental negative impact of these technologies and their applications. Currently, there is no methodology yet to rank those according to environmental footprint. This research will also inform some ISO development on auditing guidelines regarding the issue of organisational risks.

The priority is to address the lack of standards and scientific research recognised at the world level on this topic requires to development of a set of standards from which to understand and manage the environmental impact of Blockchains and Distributed ledger technologies. On the other hand, these technologies are usually classified based on the consensus mechanisms which represent the "backbone" of developments. Consequently, this research initially will focus on the preliminary work to develop a Technical Report on the environmental sustainability classification methodology of the consensus mechanisms of Blockchain and DLTs. It will be the key input for developing posterior research to provide a complementary classification of applications based on Blockchain and DLTs which can serve as a basis for labelling these technologies and crypto assets according to categories of energy efficiency, among other goals.

Finally, the challenge is that this research requires a multi-domain approach integrated into one research, to facilitate a common language between experts on DLTs, Sustainability, and Innovation Management. One of the main challenges this research faces is the lack of substantial scientific research in the domain. Although there are some scientific papers

related, however, due to the market changes and the dispersion of Blockchain solutions and DLTs in general the degree of relevance of the academic input is also very limited and in some scientific papers not reliable due to the lack of empirical validations to support the theoretical assumptions.

Concerned ICT Standards and contribution to the related landscape

CEN and CENELEC, consider the Green Transition as a priority and have identified the digital and green twin transition as a core driver for their joint 2030 Strategy, recognising that standards are a critical enabler of the solutions needed for the Green Deal transition.

On the other hand, The EU commitment, the political priorities and the social pressure for the fight against climate change make the need for environmental sustainability methodologies to understand and classify the potential ICT solutions, it becomes critical to support the Green Deal goal's purpose.

For instance, the new Eco-design legislation and the digital product passport proposal highlight the need to include decentralised identifiers and interoperable with centralised solutions is highlighted. To ensure trust, stakeholder engagement and adoption of the DPP, it is needed to include environmental considerations.

In this framework, my fellowship research supports a set of standards at CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 WG 2 Environmental Sustainability of Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT).

- ▶ Technical Report, Environmental sustainability classification methodology of consensus mechanisms of Blockchain and DLT.
- ▶ New work item proposal of technical specification: Environmental Sustainability Taxonomy of Blockchain and DLT.

On the other hand, the research would inform a set of standards in development under the JTC 24 Digital Product Passport (DPP), which highlights the need to include decentralised identifiers and interoperable with centralised solutions. To ensure trust, stakeholder engagement and adoption of the DPP by disclosing the environmental considerations of the final solution itself.

At the ISO TC 307 WG5 Governance, it would be useful for the development of a guideline standard on auditing. The research output can represent a key input for informing the organisational risk in terms of Environmental, Social and Governance indicators.

At the high level, ICT standards must establish a framework for ensuring trust, interoperability and interoperation via secure and reliable applications, as well as facilitate the stakeholder's engagement. This research contributes to this goal by facilitating understanding and environmental impact management of the Blockchain and DLTs.

Impact (on European SMEs, related projects or in society)

Impact on SMEs

In the pre-commercial and commercial stages of Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies applications, stakeholder engagement and adoption represent one of the main bottlenecks. To guide the applications to provide environmental sustainability information and easier compliance with the new EU legislation, this research will allow the attraction of investment and stakeholders' adoption when the application and technologies are developed from proactive risk and environmental impact management and including the energy consumption criteria. It also promotes trust and interoperability, comparability and integrability of applications, and contributes to the Digital Single Market. The environmental classification methodologies proposed could allow a better understanding and comprehension of environmental sustainability for better impact management and provide trust.

FIGURE 14 EXAMPLE OF A FELLOWSHIP STORY

FIGURE 15 EXAMPLE OF THE IMPACT REPORT BRANDING

Moreover, as StandICT.eu Programme has continued evolving since 2018, the StandICT.eu partners have perceived that the continuous publication and promotion of the quality impact reports also has the benefit of contributing to the quality of the fellowship applications, as the applicants can consult information about the previously funded activities, which helps them to align better their fellowship project with the programme's expectations.

AUSTRALO manages the daily monitoring of the fellowships with continuous support from Trust-IT, as explained in Section 2. Therefore, these two partners collaborate closely in drafting and editing the impact reports; AUSTRALO manages the initial data collection from the fellows drafting the structures of all success stories whilst Trust-IT performs the editing and outlaying of the report following the branding system defined in the project's Communication Strategy (D6.1) and used for each of the Open calls.

The public promotion of the Impact Reports is carried out through the channels of the well-established StandICT.eu 2026 communication, including:

- Dedicated articles on StandICT.eu website
- Dedicated Press releases
- One-to-one message campaigns to the stakeholders
- Availability on the Open Access Library "Zenodo"
- Social Media Campaigns
- Featuring in StandICT.eu 2026 Webinars
- Featuring in the project newsletters.

4.1.1 Impact Report 1

The first impact report under StandICT.eu 2026 was released March 2024. Since its publication, this document records **924 views and 101 downloads**.

Read the entire report here: <https://zenodo.org/records/10809954>

FIGURE 16 OPEN CALL 1 REPORT BANNER

4.1.2 Impact Report 2

The second Impact Report was published in May 2024, and since its publication, this document records **86 views and 57 downloads**.

Read the entire report here: <https://zenodo.org/records/11104977>

FIGURE 17 OPEN CALL 2 REPORT BANNER

4.2 Forthcoming Impact Reports

The StandICT.eu 2026 continues to regularly issue the new editions of the impact reports. The publication timing of each new report depends on the progress of the data collection from each funding batch, and Table 7 provides the initial publication plan that could evolve a bit, based on the fellowship programme's progress.

TABLE 7 PLAN FOR IMPACT REPORT PUBLICATIONS

Forthcoming report	Monitoring started/planned	Impact report published for
OC3 Report	March 2024	July 2024
OC4 Report	June 2024	October 2024
OC5 Report	October 2024	January 2025
OC6 Report	December 2024	March 2025
OC7 Report	February 2025	May 2025
OC8 Report	May 2025	August 2025
OC9 Report	August 2025	October 2025

4.3 Success stories

Next to the fellowship stories presented in the Impact Reports that were detailed in the past sections, we also collect success stories. StandICT.eu 2026 success stories describe initiatives that have led to concrete impactful results or show promising developments in the ICT standardisation activities of a project, a company, an institution, or even a single professional. Success stories demonstrate the benefits coming from the standardisation activities for a broad range of actors.

The success stories are presented in a dedicated page ¹⁵of StandICT.eu website, and these present following aspects of different successful standardisation initiatives: *the context, the faced challenges, How standardisation activities help face the challenges?, the benefits, and future plans.*

¹⁵ www.standict.eu/success-stories

FIGURE 18 EXAMPLE OF A SUCCESS STORY

Moreover, these are collected as part of WP5 “Engagement and synergies” activities, and the stories cover also initiatives coming from outside the project efforts and funding.

5. LESSONS LEARNT AND NEXT STEPS

The success of the StandICT.eu 2026 Fellowship Programme has been proved not only by the great number of applications to each open call, but also by the effective management and monitoring of the contracted fellowships. The tight collaboration between Trust-IT, DCU and AUSTRALO (within the WP3) has resulted in a fully functional monitoring and impact assessment strategy applied throughout the series of open calls. The team made sure that all funded fellows could easily understand and follow the monitoring process including two reports for long term fellowships (interim and final reports) and one report for one-shot and short-term projects (final report). These are submitted with respect to the set deadlines of each fellowship via TRUST-GRANTS™ platform, which enables timely follow up of the achieved results and impact of all contracted fellowships.

Impact assessment and dissemination are crucial for showcasing the concrete results of the fellowship programme in terms of contributions in ICT standards and work groups across the SDOs and the ESOs. And, with the new series of nine impact reports, dedicated to each of the open calls, presenting all fellowship stories, the project regularly demonstrates the achieved impact and showcases the expert profiles and activities to which the allocated public grants are spent.

In terms of monitoring of the fellowships, the established strategy has enabled the collection and the dissemination of the achieved results to the whole StandICT.eu community. Also, it **supported identification of challenges and mitigation of risks that could prevent fellows from completing their fellowships according to their work plans.** Moreover, frequent communication with all the funded fellows (via one-to-one messages based on the status of each fellowship) is a cornerstone of the established monitoring process. As a result, in **total 107 fellowships are currently being monitored,** in turn, resulting in over 100 fellowship reports already having been assessed and stored on Trust-Grants platform. As of May 2024 (M17), none of the retained fellows have withdrawn from the programme.

In terms of impact assessment, StandICT.eu 2026 has again started the publication series of nine Follow the Fellows Impact Reports. These publications contributed to engage with all StandICT.eu stakeholders regularly and to keep them informed about the fellowships' contributions to the global ICT standardisation. The active communication via the different established channels project supported the effective dissemination of the impact reports to a critical mass of stakeholders, which contributed to attract new potential experts applying in the forthcoming StandICT.eu open calls.

The important novelty in the StandICT.eu 2026 iteration is the monitoring process of the new **confidential “Early warning system”**, where the funded fellows can share to the members of the European Commission their observations of ICT standardisation practices that are against the European values, policies or regulations. Also, a new dedicated guideline to applicants will be released before Open Call 5 to address all the doubts received in the previous OCs, which will to further improve the experience of fellows and applicants.

During the second half of StandICT.eu 2026 Programme, the objective is to make even **stronger connections between the Fellowship programmer's funded experts and the other running activities of the project,** including the varied StandICT.eu events and expert groups. We also continue adjusting the monitoring framework and the content of monitoring reports if necessary.

ANNEX 1 – STANDICT.EU 2026 FELLOWSHIP INTERIM REPORT TEMPLATE

Interim Fellowship Report

Only For Long Term Projects

Scope

*The purpose of the present report serves the European ICT Standardisation community and National and global Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs) to advance a broader **understanding** on principal **standards** activities going on in the ICT sectors. We aim to share **high-level findings** from these reports to the **European Commission (EC)** related Directorates and to members of the **Multi Stakeholder Platform (MSP)**, with the intent to have major results cited as part of the future ICT Rolling Plan of Standardisation. Also, we will use your report data to disseminate your fellowship results in a series of Fellowship Programme Impact Reports.*

Section 1 - Fellow Profile Information

1.1 Which of the following genders describe you the best? [Drop down list we several options possible]

- Female
- Male
- I prefer not to say.

1.2 Your short professional bio in few lines [Free text - **limit 1000 char.**]

1.3 Your photo, please add the image [Requested size: 800px 800px]

1.4 For how long have you been working in ICT standards? Please, indicate in years. [Drop-down menu with numbers]

1.5 Dissemination agreement - do you consent that the StandICT.eu team uses the information above to communicate your project & results in the StandICT.eu community? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
- No

Section 2 - Progress Reporting

2.1 Indicate which gaps, priorities or challenges you are addressing? Please describe these three aspects. [Free text – **limit 2000 char.**]

2.2 How is your funded application contributing to the ICT Standards landscape, and can you name the ICT Standards you are dealing with? [Free text – **limit 2000 char.**]

2.3 Are you a contributor to a Working Group WG (s) or Technical Committee TC(s) as a part of your fellowship? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, please provide its full name: SDO + WG/ TC Number and Title [Free text, **limit 1000 char.**]
- No

2.4 Does your contribution impact European SMEs and/or European societies? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, please elaborate how [Free text, **limit 1000 char.**]
- No

2.5 In the framework of your fellowship, have you collaborated with any Associations or any EU, or National project(s)? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, which ones? [Free text – **limit 2000 char.**]
- No

2.6 Is your project directly involved or leading to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing new or revised standards?

- Yes
 - If yes, please elaborate and name the related standard [Free text, **limit 1000 char.**]
- No

2.7 What is the status of your contribution? [Drop-down menu with several possible options]

- Pending
- In progress
- Finalized
- Submitted
- Delayed

2.7.1 Please explain shortly the selected response [Free text – limit 1000 char.]

2.8 Have you contributed to the StandICT.eu [EUOS Technical Work Groups](#) (TWGs) within the context of your project? [Drop down menu with one possible option]

- Yes,
 - If yes, in which Technical Working Group (TWG) and what kind of contribution? [Free text – limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.9 As a part of your standardisation activities, have you observed any draft standards being processed that are against European values, policies, or regulations? Or have you witnessed any behaviour obstructing or delaying the ongoing standardisation work? *Please note that this information will be kept entire anonymous and shared confidentially only with the European Commission.*

- Yes
 - If yes, please elaborate your response [Free text – limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.10 Do you have any other updates, comments, or concerns regarding your fellowship that you would like to share with the StandICT.eu team? [Drop down menu with one possible option]

- Yes,
 - If yes, please share with us! [Free text – limit 2000 char.]
- No

2.11 Will you avail of future Open call StandICT.eu funding opportunities to pursue your work further? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, in which TC / WG? [Free text – limit 500 char.]
- No

ANNEX 2: STANDICT.EU 2026 FELLOWSHIP FINAL REPORT TEMPLATE

Final Fellowship Report

Scope

The purpose of the present report is to serve the European ICT Standardisation community and National and global Standards Developing Organisations (SDOs) to advance a broader **understanding** of principal **standards** activities going on in the ICT sectors. We aim to share **high-level findings** from these reports to the **European Commission (EC)** related Directorates and to members of the **Multi-Stakeholder Platform (MSP)**, with the intent to have major results cited as part of the future ICT Rolling Plan of Standardisation. Also, we will use your report data to disseminate your fellowship results in a series of Fellowship Programme Impact Reports.

Section 1 - Fellow Profile Information

1.1 Which of the following genders describes you the best? [Drop-down the list we several options possible]

- Female
- Male
- I prefer not to say.

1.2 Your short professional bio in a few lines [Free text - **limit 1000 char.**]

1.3 Your photo, please add the image [Requested size: 800px 800px]

1.4 How long have you worked in ICT standards? Please, indicate in years. [Drop-down menu with numbers]

1.4.1 How were you trained to work on the ICT standardisation development?

[Free text – **limit 1000 char.**]

1.5 Dissemination agreement - do you consent that the StandICT.eu team uses the information provided here above to communicate your project & results in the StandICT.eu community? [Drop down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
- No

Section 2 - Progress Reporting

2.1 Indicate which gaps, priorities or challenges you are addressing with this fellowship? Please describe these three aspects. [Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.2 How is your funded application contributing to the ICT Standards landscape, and can you name the ICT Standards you are dealing with? [Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.3 Are you a contributor to a Working Group WG (s) or Technical Committee TC (s) as a part of your fellowship? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, please provide its full name: SDO + WG/ TC Number + Title [Free text, limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.4 From your perspective, how do you see that this WG / TC could contribute or is contributing to the [ICT Standardisation Rolling plan](#) action points? Please elaborate [Free text, limit 1000 char.]

2.5 Does your contribution impact European SMEs in any way? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Yes
 - If yes, please elaborate [Free text, limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.6 In the framework of your fellowship, have you collaborated with any other Associations or any EU or national project(s)?

- Yes
 - If yes, which ones? [Free text, limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.7 To monitor your fellowship footprint (in KPIs), please indicate in numbers how many contributions you have performed until now as a part of your fellowship within the WG/TC:

2.7.1 Participating in WG meetings [drop down menu with numbers]

2.7.2 Attendance in Webinars or Workshops [drop down menu with numbers]

2.7.3 Delivered publication, report or deliverable [drop down menu with numbers]

2.7.4 Other, please specify [Free text – limit 1000 char.]

2.8 Could you describe these achieved contributions within your fellowship shortly?

[Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.9 What societal impacts did your work support? [Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.10 As a part of your standardisation activities, have you observed any draft standards being processed that are against European values, policies, or regulations? Or have you witnessed any behaviour obstructing or delaying the ongoing standardisation work? *Please note that this information will be kept entirely anonymous and shared confidentially only with the European Commission.*

- Yes
 - If yes, **please elaborate your response** [Free text – limit 1000 char.]
- No

2.11 What state of maturity is the standard of your topic in general?

- Very mature
- Mature
- Preliminary phase
- Other states of maturity, please specify [Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.12 Please indicate your recommendations in pursuing the work on the concerned standard or specification. [Drop down menu with one possible]

- Suggest continuation of action
- Additional EU experts needed to better support the EU position
- Action Successfully finalised
- No further action required

2.12.1 Please elaborate on the selected response [Free text – limit 2000 char.]

2.13 Has your project directly involved or led to a specific recommendation or proposal for developing a new standard, or was it aimed at supporting the revision of an existing standard? [Drop-down menu with one possible option + free text]

- Yes
 - If yes, **please specify the new or revised standard and name it.** [Free text – **limit 1000 char.**]
- No
- I don't know

2.14 Have the standardisation activities in your project led to specific deliverables? [Drop-down menu with one possible option]

- Technical Specifications
- Technical Report
 - Common Terminology
 - Development of a news standard
 - Reference Data
 - Recommendations for new/revised standards
 - Reference material
 - New Operating procedure
 - Other, please specify:

2.15 Has your fellowship contributed to a new Technical Group or Work Group?

- Yes
 - If yes, please detail which one? [Free text – **limit 1000 char.**]
- No

2.16 Are you a chair, convener, or moderator of any WG or Technical Committee group?

- Yes
 - If yes, **please, specify the position and name the SDO/ TC / WG**
- No

2.17 What is the status of your contribution, and when is the expected date of the target release or publication of your work?

- Pending
- In progress
- Finalized
- Submitted
- Delayed
 - Justify the selected response [Free text – [Free text – **limit 1000 char.**]

- Not relevant (for One-Shot projects)

2.18 Have you shared your outcomes or joined discussions on the EUOS within the context of your project?

- Yes,
 - If yes, in which Work Group? ([Free text – [Free text – **limit 1000 char.**]
- No

2.19 Please indicate the StandICT.eu EUOS Technical Work Group (TWG) in which you have contributed as a part of your fellowship [Drop down list with one possible option]

- TWG-Artificial Intelligence
- TWG-Trusted Information
- TWG-Smart Cities
- TWG-Digital Twin
- TWG-Internet of Things & Edge Computing
- TWG-Data Driven Policy
- TWG-Digital Product Passport
- TWG-Ontologies
- TWG-Robotics
- TWG-Block Chain
- TWG-Cybersecurity
- TWG-Trusted & Secure Chips
- TWG-Big Data Spaces and Data Interoperability
- TWG-Intelligent Computing
- TWG-Quantum Technologies

2.19.1 Please define in which deliverable type you have contributed to [Drop down list with one possible option]

- Landscape & gap analysis
- Policy recommendations
- Other, please name it [Free text – **limit 500 char.**]

2.19.2 Please describe your contributions regarding actions and delivered work items in the EUOS WG

2.20 Please provide any public links available to demonstrate your work. Provide at least the webpage of the TC / WG related to your fellowship. [Free text – **limit 2000 char.**]

2.21 Please use this free text space to include any additional items you'd like to share that are not covered above. [Free text –limit 2000 char.]

2.22 Will you avail of future Open call StandICT.eu funding opportunities to pursue your work further? [Drop down menu with one possible option]

- Yes,
 - If yes, for which action? [Free text – limit 2000 char.]
- No

2.23 Attachment - please add any attachments to justify your work.

2.24 We are collecting examples of Success Stories that have led to concrete, impactful results or show promising developments in the ICT standardisation activities to demonstrate the benefits of the standardisation activities for a broad range of actors (projects, companies, research institutions, or professionals). **Do you agree that the StandICT.eu team drafts a success story of your fellowship project based on the data provided in this report?** This story will be published here: [/www.standict.eu/success-stories](http://www.standict.eu/success-stories) . Please note that any sensitive information will not be made public.

- Yes, I agree.
- No, I disagree.

Thank you!

ANNEX 3 – LIST OF FUNDED FELLOWS UNDER OC#1

First Name	Surname	Focused ICT sector	Engaged SDO	WG / TC name
Erik	Andersen	Cybersecurity	ITU	ITU-T Study Group 17 Q11 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6 WG 10
Christophe	Stenuit	Cybersecurity	ISO/IEC	SDO CEN/CLC/JTC 13 WG5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management; SDO ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 on Identity management and privacy technologies
Robert	Mueller	Cybersecurity	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification
Jan	Lindquist	E-privacy	CEN	ISO SC27/WG5 (identity management and privacy technologies), CEN JTC 13/WG5 (data protection, privacy and identity management), CEN TC 224 WG20 (Ad hoc group on european digital identity wallet)
Julien	Bringer	E-privacy	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC 24745, CEN/ CNLC JTC 13
Octavian	Popescu	Network and information security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN CENELEC JTC 13 and working groups
Thomas	Loruenser	Network and information security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC SC27 WG2 (also active in WG3, 4, 5), Austrian Standards Institute AG 001 27
Octavian	Popescu	Network and information security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN CENELEC JTC 13.
Jordi	Mongay Batalla	Network and information security	O-RAN	O-RAN Alliance, WG11: Security Work Group, Security Testing Work Item
Ranganai	Chaparadza	5G& beyond 6G	ETSI	ETSI TC INT AFI WG; IEEE INGR Future Networks Initiative Systems Optimization WG & Standardisation Building Blocks (SBB) WG; GSMA work on Security in Future Networks; ETSI IPE ISG; ITU-T SG11; 3GPP Standards on Security in 5G; O-RAN Specifications on Security in Open RAN; IEEE Future Networks INGR Work in the Security WG; NGMN Work on Security in 5G Networks; ENISA Report on 5G Security Challenges
Alexandru	Vulpe	5G& beyond 6G	IEEE	IEEE VTS AI in Wireless Communications Committee
Patrick	Bezombes	Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21/WG 1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and ISO-IEC/SC 42/AG 3 (AI Standardisation roadmapping)

Agnieszka	Rządowska	Artificial intelligence	Cross-SDO	EITCI SMART-PV-SESG (Smart Energy Standards Group hosted under EITCI Institute), CENELEC / IEC-TC CLC/TC-82 (Solar photovoltaic energy systems) and the CLC/TC-57 (Power systems management and associated information exchange) for power systems control equipment and systems including EMS (Energy Management Systems) and SCADA (Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition)
Francisco	Medeiros-Filho	Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	Focus during the period will be on CEN/CENELEC JTC21 side, the intention is to continue my leadership role (Co-Convenor) of JTC21 WG1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and Head of the Belgian delegations to ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC. My additional target: co-lead the newly established Task Group on AI Cybersecurity within JTC21 WG1.
Adam	Smith	Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 / WG 3
Alessio	Tartaro	Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG 4 - Foundational and social aspects
Rami	Mochaourab	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC	Swedish Institute for Standards SIS/TK 611 Informationsteknik, Arbetsgrupp (AG) 03 Artificiell Intelligens
Carlos	Zednik	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 – Artificial Intelligence, Working Group 3 – Trustworthiness
Viveka	Bonde	Artificial intelligence	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG3 (Trustworthiness)
Enrico	Panai	Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CNE/CLC/JTC21 project on “AI Conformity assessment” (WG2), project on “ Data Governance and data quality for AI in the European context” (WG2), project on “ Check List for AI Risks Management “ (WG2) and project on “AI trustworthiness characterization” (WG4), AFNOR (ethics committee on AI), ISO/IEC SC 42 JTC1 WG3 on “AI trustworthiness”, Others
Thomas	Frisendal	Big data, open data and public sector information	ISO/IEC	ISO IEC/JTC1/ SC32/WG3 Database languages
Caroline	Thomas	Blockchain	ISO	ISO/TC307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies
Julien	Bringer	Electronic identification	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17, CEN/ CNLC JTC 13, CEN/TC 224/WG18
Maria Ines	Robles	IoT	IETF	IETF ROLL Working Group, IETF IoT-Directorate, IETF Routing-Directorate, IETF Gen-Area Review Team
Witold	Jacak	Quantum technology	CEN/CENELEC	EITCI OQP-QSG, CEN/CENELEC FGQT

Richard	Pitwon	Quantum technology	IEC	IEC SEG 14 on Quantum Technologies, IEC TC 86/JWG 9 - Optical functionality for electronic assemblies (Optical circuit boards), IEC TC86 / SC86B (Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components)
Michele	Amoretti	Quantum technology	CEN/CENELEC	UNI/CT 535 "Quantum Technologies" CEN/CENELEC JTC 22 "Quantum Technologies" WG1 "Strategic Advisory Group" and Working Group 3" Quantum Computing and Simulation".
Belen	Suarez	Digital product passport	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELC JTC 19 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG 2 Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and DLTs; CEN/CENELEC Standardisation Request Ad-hoc group (SRAHG) on Digital Product Passport
Paulo	Gonçalves	Robotics and autonomous systems	IEEE	IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots; IEEE WG 1872.1 - Robot Task Representation; IEEE WG 3140 - Semantic Map for Autonomous Robots Working Group ; IEEE WG 3107: Human-Robot Interaction Terminology ; IEEE WG 3108: Recommended Practice for Human-Robot Interaction Design of Human Subject Studies
Jérôme	François	ICT environmental impact	IETF	NMRG
Marius	Preda	Metaverse	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 7 MPEG Coding for 3D Graphics and Haptics; ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 2 MPEG Requirements
Pilar	Orero	Metaverse	ITU	ITU Focus Group on Metaverse, Working Group 8 Accessibility and inclusion
Alex	Cadzow	Artificial intelligence	ETSI	ETSI TC SAI
Marios	Angelopoulos	Smart cities	ITU	ITU-T Study Group 20 Internet of things (IoT) and smart cities and communities (SC&C)
Karim	Tobich	Cloud computing	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC/JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection/WG1 Information security management systems

ANNEX 4 – LIST OF FUNDED FELLOWS UNDER OC#2

First Name	Surname	Focused ICT sector	Main Engaged SDO	WG / TC name
Francisco	Medeiros-Filho	Artificial Intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	JTC21 WG1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and Head of the Belgian delegation to CEN/CENELEC JTC21.
Enrico	Panai	Artificial Intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CNE/CLC/JTC21 project on “AI Conformity assessment” (WG2), project on “ Data Governance and data quality for AI in the European context” (WG2), project on “ Check List for AI Risks Management “ (WG2) and project on “AI trustworthiness characterization” (WG4), AFNOR (ethics committee on AI), ISO/IEC SC 42 JTC1 WG3 on “AI trustworthiness”, "Ethics"
Mauro	Dragoni	Artificial Intelligence	ETSI	ETSI SmartM2M (Machine-To-Machine) Communication Working Group and ETSI OCG (Operational Co-ordination Group) on Artificial Intelligence.
Jurriaan	Parie	Artificial Intelligence	OTHER	CEN/CLC/JTC 21 “Artificial Intelligence” WG 2-4 Operational, Engineering, Foundational and Societal aspects
Lauriane	Aufrant	Artificial Intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CLC/JTC 21 “Artificial Intelligence” (contributing to WG 1 “Strategic Advisory Group” and WG 3 “Engineering Aspects”), ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC 42 “Artificial Intelligence” (contributing to WG 1 “Foundational standards”, WG 3 “Trustworthiness”, WG 5 “Computational approaches and computational characteristics of Artificial Intelligence systems”), AFNOR/CN IA “Artificial Intelligence”, ISO/TC 37 “Language and terminology”
Sebastian	Posth	Artificial Intelligence	ISO	ISO/TC 46/SC 9/WG 18 – ISO/DIS 24138 – International Standard Content Code
Carlos Luis	Parra-Calderón	Artificial Intelligence	ISO	Snomed CT, OHDSI-OMOP, WHO ICD, LOINC
Peter	Baumann	Big Data	ISO	ISO TC211 WG6 Geographic Imagery

Geoffrey	Goodell	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	ISO/TC 307/WG 1 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology - Foundations, ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1 Archives/Records Management - Blockchain, ISO/TC 307/AG 1 SBP Review Advisory Group, ISO/TC 307/AG 3 Digital Currencies, ISO/TC 68/AG 5 Digital Currencies, ISO/TC 68/SC 8/WG 3 Digital Token Identifier
Panos	Kudumakis	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup Reference standards: ISO/IEC 21000-19 Media Value Chain Ontology (MVCO), 21000-19/AMD1 Audio Value Chain Ontology (AVCO), 21000-20 Contract Expression Language (CEL), 21000-21 Media Contract Ontology (MCO), ISO/IEC 21000-23 Smart Contracts for Media
Paull	Ferris	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	ISO/TC 307 ISO/TC 307/AG 1 - Convenor AG1 Strategic Business Plan Review Advisor Group, CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01 "Decentralised identity management", ISO/TC 307 - Technical Expert WG5 Governance, ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in JWG4 Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain, ISO/TC307 - Technical Expert in WG3 Smart Contracts and DLT ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in WG6 Use Cases ISO/TC 307/CAG 1 Convenor and ISO/TC215, Liaison Medical Informatics, CEN/CLC/JTC 19 "Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies"
Caroline	Thomas	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies ISO/TC 307 Convenor or WG6, and technical expert to WG1 Foundational, JWG4 Security and Privacy, WG5 Governance, WG7 Interoperability, AG3 Digital Currencies
Christian	Grafenauer	Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO/IEC	ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies
Pierre-François	Jullien	Building Information Modelling	CEN	CEN/TC442/WG2/PT5. EN ISO 23386, EN ISO 12006-3, EN 17549-2
Leandro	Navarro	Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport	ITU	Q7/SG5
Alex	Cadzow	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ETSI	ETSI TC CYBER

Erik	Andersen	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 2, "Cryptography and security mechanisms" is working on development. of cryptographic algorithms and will be involved and their standards are referenced.
Octavian	Popescu	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN / CENELEC JTC13, CEN / CENELEC JTC13 WG 9
Pavel	Cuchriajev	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification
François	LOREK	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AhG2, AhG3 & WG4; CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2, WG3, AhG3 and AhG8 and JTC13 ISO JTC1 SC40 WG1 and WG2, SC41 and SC42 WG1 and WG3
Christophe	Stenuit	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ISO/IEC	SDO CEN/CLC/JTC 13 WG5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management; SDO ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 on Identity management and privacy technologies
Octavian	Popescu	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN CENELEC JTC 13 and working groups, ETSI TC CYBER
Thierry	MAXIME	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO JTC1 WG4; including ISO TC292 WG2, CEN/CENELEC JTC13
Johann	Groszschaedl	Cybersecurity NetworkAnd Information Security	IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), Working Group for Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ace) and Working Group for Lightweight Implementation Guidance (lwig)
Kung	Antonio	Data Economy	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27, SC38, SC41
Pablo	Vicente Legazpi	Digitisation Of European Industry	CEN	CEN442 WG9 and liasons with WG4 and WG2
Raul	SANCHEZ-REILLO	E-Identification and Trust Services	CEN	CEN/TC 224/WG 20, ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17 AG3, ETSI ESI & eIDAS EU Expert Group

Ieva	Kersiene	E-Identification and Trust Services	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17/WG11
Robert	Mueller	E-Identification and Trust Services	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC37 WG3
Tony	Allen	Fin Tech and Reg Tech Standardisation	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG5 - Identity and Privacy Management
Loïc	Blaive	Intelligent Transport Systems	CEN	CEN/TC 278/WG 7 - ISO/TC 204/WG 3 - ISO/TC 211/JWG 11
Kate	Grant	Internet Of Things	IEC	IEC Systems Committee on Active Assisted Living, IEC Systems Committee on Smart Cities, ISO/IEC JTC 1 - Information technology, IEC TC 100 Audio, video and multimedia systems and equipment, IEC Systems committee on Communications Technologies and Architectures and JTC 1 SC41 IoT and Digital Twin.
Muslim	Elkotob	5G and beyond, 6G	ETSI	ITU-T SG11 and Focus Group on Testbeds Federations, , ETSI TC INT and ETSI AFI, IEEE (INGR), TM Forum Catalyst Program (Current Catalyst C23.0.472) and others
Homer	Papadopoulos	Quantum Technologies	CEN/CENELEC	Cen Cenelec JTC 22, QuIC Standardisation Working Group
Marco	Azpúrua	Smart Grids And Smart Metering	IEC	CISPR\CIS A\JWG 9: Rapid emission check of installations. Other related standards are CISPR 37, CISPR 11 and CISPR 16-2-5. IEC TC82 and CENELEC TC219 of PLC are very interested as well.
João Manuel	Leitão Quintas	Smart Grids And Smart Metering	IEEE	IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots, IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group
Olivier	Genest	Smart Grids And Smart Metering	IEC	IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3, IEC SyC Smart Energy CAG, ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG6, CEN/CLC/ ETSI CG-SG

ANNEX 5 – LIST OF FUNDED FELLOWS UNDER OC#3

First Name	Surname	Focused ICT sector	Main Engaged SDO	WG / TC name
Ranganai	Chaparadza	5G and beyond, 6G	ITU-T	ITU-T Focus Group FG-TBFxG on on Testbeds Federations for 5G and Beyond; ETSI TC Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT)/ Autonomic Management and Control (AMC) Intelligence for Self-Managed Fixed & Mobile Integrated Networks (AFI) WG ETSI TR 103 763; NIST Multi-Domain Knowledge Planes for Service Federation for 5G & Beyond Public Working Group (MDKP-PWG); IEEE INGR Future Networks Initiative Systems Optimization WG & Testbeds WG & Standardisation Building Blocks (SBB) WG;
Alojz	Hudobivnik	5G and beyond, 6G	ITU-T	ITU-T SG13 - Future networks and emerging network technologies ; WP1/13 "IMT-2020 and Beyond: Networks & Systems"; ITU-T Y.xxxx series of standards
Andrea	Basso	Artificial Intelligence	IEEE	P7018 - Standard for Security and Trustworthiness Requirements in Generative Pretrained Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models
Piercosma	Bisconti Lucidi	Artificial Intelligence	CEN-CENELEC	CEN-CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence WG4 Foundational and societal aspects
Rania	Wazir	Artificial Intelligence	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 JWG5 "Natural language processing" (Joint WG with ISO/TC 37); CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG3 "Engineering aspects"
Alessio	Tartaro	Artificial Intelligence	CEN-CENELEC	CEN-CENELEC JTC 21 WG 4 - Foundational and social aspects
Javier	Peris	Artificial Intelligence	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 "Artificial Intelligence".
Agnieszka	Rządowska	Artificial Intelligence	EITCI	EITCI SMART-PV-SESG (Smart Energy Standards Group hosted under EITCI Institute), CENELEC / IEC-TC CLC/TC-82 (Solar photovoltaic energy systems) and the CLC/TC-57 (Power systems management and associated information exchange) for power systems control equipment and systems including EMS (Energy Management Systems) and SCADA (Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition)

Domenico	Natale	Artificial Intelligence	ISO/IEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG3 Engineering Aspects CEN/CENELEC JTC21 AI WG2 Operational aspects ISO/IEC SC7 WG6 Product quality ISO/IEC SC42 - WG3 Trustworthiness ISO/IEC SC42 WG2 Data
Christophe	Ozcan	Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	ISO/TC 307/WG 3 Smart Contracts and their applications
Paull	Ferris	Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	ISO/TC 307 ISO/TC 307/AG 1 - Convenor AG1 Strategic Business Plan Review Advisor Group, CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01 "Decentralised identity management", ISO/TC 307 - Technical Expert WG5 Governance, ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in JWG4 Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain, ISO/TC307 - Technical Expert in WG3 Smart Contracts and DLT ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in WG6 Use Cases ISO/TC 307/CAG 1 Convenor and ISO/TC215, Liaison Medical Informatics, CEN/CLC/JTC 19 "Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies"
Julian	Lauten-Weiss	Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport	CEN	CEN Ad Hoc Group Information sharing; Ad Hoc Group EU Circular Economy Terminology, Framework & Principles; Ad Hoc Group Extended producer responsibility; Ad Hoc Group Circular Business models Ad Hoc Group EU Circular Economy Terminology, Framework & Principles Ad Hoc Group Extended producer responsibility Ad Hoc Group Circular business models
Christophe	Stenuit	Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CLC/JTC 13 WG5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management; SDO ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 on Identity management and privacy technologies
Elzbieta	Andrukiewicz	Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27/WG3 "Security evaluation, testing and specification"
Samia	Oukemeni	Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	IEEE	IEEE INGR SysOpt (that I am a core member of); INGR stands for International Network Generations Roadmap and represents different tracks for Standardisation and innovation, with SysOpt focusing on System Optimization with focus on Standards.
Angie	Garry Jaegermann	Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	CEN-CENELEC	CEN/CLC/JTC22; WG1- Strategic Advisory Group(SAG); WG2- Quantum Metrology, Sensing and Enhanced Imaging, and Quantum Enabling Technologies; WG3- Quantum Computing and Simulation; WG4- Quantum Communication and Quantum Cryptography.

				CEN/CLC/JTC21 WG1 TG Cybersecurity for AI systems supporting the AI Act. (This task group will continue the activity under new WG5)
Sandra	Feliciano	Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	CEN	CEN/TC 353 Information and Communication Technologies for Learning, Education and Training (where a new working group will need to be established and mandated with this new work item proposal)
Caroline	Thomas	E-Infrastructure For Data And Computing Intensive Service	ISO	ISO/TC 307 Convenor of WG6 Use Cases, and technical expert to AG1 SBP Review Advisory Group, CAG1 Chairs Advisory Board, WG1 Foundational, JWG4 Security and Privacy, WG5 Governance, WG7 Interoperability, AG3 Digital Currencies.
Jan	Lindquist	Electronic Identification and Trust Services	CEN	CEN/TC 224 WG20; ISO SC27 WG5
Michal	Tabor	Electronic Identification and Trust Services	ETSI	ETSI ESI
Robert	MUELLER	Electronic Identification and Trust Services	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Cards and security devices for personal identification
Raul	SANCHEZ-REILLO	Electronic Identification and Trust Services	CEN	CEN TC224 WG18, ETSI/ESI, ISO/IEC JTC1/SC37 WG5, Common Criteria (including BIO-iTC community), FIDO & eIDAS EU Expert Group
Julien	Bringer	Electronic Identification and Trust Services	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17, CEN/ CNLC JTC 13, CEN/TC 224/WG18
Julien	Bringer	E-Privacy	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 3, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC 24745, CEN/ CNLC JTC 13
Matthieu	Briottet	E-Privacy	CEN-CENELEC	CEN-CLC/JTC 13 'Cybersecurity and Data Protection', Working Group 5 'Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management'
Amelie	Gyrard	Internet of Things	ISO	ISO SC41 IoT and Digital Twin, ISO SC 42 AI, ISO TC215 Health Informatics
Theofanis	Raptis	Internet of Things	ITU-T	Qi standard, Wireless PowerShare
Josef	Preishuber-Pflügl	Internet of Things	ETSI	ETSI ERM TG34 "RFID"

Sebastian	Wagner	Internet of Things	3DPP	3GPP Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network (TSG RAN), RAN WG1 (RAN1)
Torbjörn	Lahrin	Metaverse Including Civerse	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1
Jacak	Witold	Quantum Technologies	EITCI	EITCI QSG-QRNG, CEN/CENELEC JTC 22
Marcello	Caleffi	Quantum Technologies	IETF	IETF Quantum Internet Research Group
Paulo	Gonçalves	Robotics and Autonomous Systems	IEEE	IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots; IEEE WG 3140 - Semantic Map for Autonomous Robots Working Group ; IEEE WG 1872.1.1: Guide for the Practical Implementation of IEEE RAS Standard 1872.1 on Robotic Task Representation.
Gero	Gschwendtner	Smart and Sustainable Cities	ISO	ISO/TC 178 Lifts, escalators and moving walks; ISO/TC 178/WG 4/6; CEN/TC 10 Lifts, escalators and moving walks; CEN/TC 10/ WG 2; ON AG 017 Aufzüge, Fahrtreppen und Fahrsteige; ON AG 017.02; Joint Working Group (JWG) CEN/TC 10 + SESA + SAC/TC 196 + CEA; CEN/TC 10/WG 2 - SAC/TC 196 joint working group; Global Technical Advisory Group of Worldwide Elevator and Escalator Federation (WEEF)
Olivier	Genest	Smart Grids and Smart Metering	IEC	IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3, IEC SyC Smart Energy CAG, ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG6, CEN/CLC/ETSI CG-SG

ANNEX 6 – INVOLVED STANDARDISATION ORGANISATIONS, WORKING GROUPS AND TECHNICAL COMMITTEES

ICT Sector	Standardisation Organisation	Technical Committee / Working group
Foundational Drivers		
Data Economy	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection ISO/IEC SC38 Cloud computing and distributed platforms ISO/IEC SC41 Internet of things and digital twin
Cybersecurity	ITU	ITU-T Study Group 17 Q11 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6 WG 10 ISO/IEC SC17 Cards and personal identification WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG3 Security evaluation, testing and specification
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG2 Cryptography and security mechanisms ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG4 Security controls and services ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AhG2 Security and privacy in IoT and Digital Twin ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AhG3 Security and privacy in AI and Big Data (BD) ISO/IEC JTC1 SC40 IT service management and IT governance ISO/IEC JTC1 SC40 WG1 Governance of InformationTechnology ISO/IEC JTC1 SC40 WG2 Service management – Information technology ISO/IEC JTC1 SC41 Internet of things and digital twin ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 Artificial intelligence ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG1 Foundational standards ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG3 Trustworthiness
	IEEE	IEEE INGR System Optimization SysOpt

	<p>CEN-CENELEC</p> <p>CEN / CENELEC JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection CEN / CENELEC JTC 13 WG5 on Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management CEN / CENELEC JTC13 WG 9 Special Working Group on Cyber Resilience Act CEN / CENELEC JTC21 Artificial Intelligence WG1 TG Cybersecurity for AI systems CEN / CENELEC JTC 21 WG2 Cryptography and security mechanisms CEN / CENELEC JTC 21 WG3 Security evaluation, testing and specification CEN / CENELEC JTC 21 AhG3 Security and privacy in AI and Big Data (BD) CEN / CENELEC JTC 21 AG8 Advisory Group on Conformity Assessment CEN / CENELEC JTC22 Quantum Technologies WG1 Strategic Advisory Group(SAG) CEN / CENELEC JTC22 WG2- Quantum Metrology, Sensing and Enhanced Imaging, and Quantum Enabling Technologies CEN / CENELEC JTC22 WG3- Quantum Computing and Simulation CEN / CENELEC JTC22 WG4- Quantum Communication and Quantum Cryptography.</p> <p>CEN</p> <p>CEN/TC 353 Information and Communication Technologies for Learning, Education and Training</p> <p>ETSI</p> <p>ETSI TC CYBER</p> <p>IETF</p> <p>Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF), Working Group for Authentication and Authorization for Constrained Environments (ace) and Working Group for Lightweight Implementation Guidance (Iwig)</p>
Network and information security	<p>CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>CEN /CENELEC JTC 13 Cybersecurity</p> <p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection WG2 Cryptography and security mechanisms</p> <p>O-RAN</p> <p>O-RAN Alliance, WG11: Security Work Group, Security Testing Work Item</p>
E-privacy	<p>CEN</p> <p>CEN TC 224 WG20 Ad hoc group on european digital identity wallet</p>

	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3 Security evaluation, testing and specification ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37 Biometrics ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37 WG5 Biometric testing and reporting
	CEN-CENELEC	CEN-CLC/JTC 13 'Cybersecurity and Data Protection', Working Group 5 'Data Protection, Privacy and Identity Management'
Key enablers and Security		
5G and beyond, 6G	ETSI	ETSI TC INT AFI WG ETSI IPE ISG
	ITU-T	ITU-T Focus Group FG-TBFxG on on Testbeds Federations for 5G and Beyond ITU-T SG13 - Future networks and emerging network technologies WP1/13 "IMT-2020 and Beyond: Networks & Systems"; ITU-T Y.xxxx series of standards
	IEEE	IEEE VTS AI in Wireless Communications Committee IEEE INGR Future Networks Initiative Systems Optimization WG & Standardisation Building Blocks (SBB) IEEE INGR Future Networks Initiative Systems Optimization WG & Testbeds WG & Standardisation Building Blocks (SBB) WG;
Cloud computing	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC/JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection/WG1 Information security management systems
Big data, open data and public sector information	ISO	ISO TC211 WG6 Geographic Imagery
	ISO/IEC	ISO IEC/JTC1/ SC32/WG3 Database languages
Internet Of Things	IEC	IEC Systems Committee on Active Assisted Living IEC Systems Committee on Smart Cities IEC TC 100 Audio, video and multimedia systems and equipment IEC Systems committee on Communications Technologies and Architectures
	ISO	ISO SC41 IoT and Digital Twin ISO SC 42 AI ISO TC215 Health Informatics
	ITU-T	Qi standard, Wireless PowerShare

	<p>ETSI 3DPP IETF</p>	<p>ETSI ERM TG34 "RFID" 3GPP Technical Specification Group Radio Access Network (TSG RAN), RAN WG1 (RAN1) IETF ROLL Working Group IETF IoT-Directorate IETF Routing-Directorate IETF Gen-Area Review Team</p>
E-Identification and Trust Services	<p>CEN/CENELEC CEN ISO/IEC</p>	<p>CEN / CENELEC JTC 13 Cybersecurity and data protection CEN/TC 224 'Personal identification and related personal devices with secure elements, systems, operations and privacy in a multi sectorial environment CEN/TC 224 WG18 Biometrics CEN/TC 224/WG 20 European Digital Identity Wallets ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17 Cards and personal identification WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 Identity management and privacy technologies ISO/IEC SC37 Biometrics WG3 Biometric data interchange formats ISO/IEC SC37 WG5 Biometric testing and reporting</p>
Quantum Technologies	<p>CEN/CENELEC EITCI IETF IEC</p>	<p>CEN /CENELEC JTC 22 Quantum Technologies QuIC Standardisation Working Group CEN /CENELEC JTC 22 WG1 "Strategic Advisory Group" CEN /CENELEC WG3 "Quantum Computing and Simulation". CEN/CENELEC FGQT EITCI QSG-QRNG IETF Quantum Internet Research Group IEC SEG 14 on Quantum Technologies IEC TC 86/JWG 9 - Optical functionality for electronic assemblies (Optical circuit boards) IEC TC86 / SC86B (Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components)</p>

<p>Artificial intelligence</p>	<p>CEN/CENELEC CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21/WG 1 (Strategic Advisory Group) CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG2 Operational aspects CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG 3 Trustworthiness CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG 4 Foundational and social aspects CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG 5 Computational approaches and computational characteristics of Artificial Intelligence systems</p> <p>ISO/IEC ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 – Artificial intelligence ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG3 (Trustworthiness) ISO/IEC JTC1/SC42 JWG5 "Natural language processing" (Joint WG with ISO/TC 37)</p> <p>AFNOR AFNOR Ethics committee on AI</p> <p>ETSI ETSI TC SAI ETSI SmartM2M (Machine-To-Machine) Communication Working Group ETSI OCG (Operational Co-ordination Group) on Artificial Intelligence.</p> <p>ISO ISO/TC 37 "Language and terminology" ISO/TC 46/SC 9/WG 18 – ISO/DIS 24138 – International Standard Content Code</p> <p>IEEE P7018 - Standard for Security and Trustworthiness Requirements in Generative Pretrained Artificial Intelligence (AI) Models</p> <p>ISO/IEC ISO/IEC SC7 WG6 Product quality ISO/IEC SC42 - WG3 Tustworthiness ISO/IEC SC42 WG2 Data</p> <p>SIS Swedish Institute for Standards SIS/TK 611 Informationsteknik, Arbetsgrupp (AG) 03 Artificiell Intelligens</p> <p>EITCI EITCI SMART-PV-SESG (Smart Energy Standards Group hosted under EITCI Institute), CENELEC / IEC-TC CLC/TC-82 (Solar photovoltaic energy systems) and the CLC/TC-57 (Power systems management and associated information exchange) for power systems control equipment and systems including EMS (Energy Management Systems) and SCADA (Supervisory Control And Data Acquisition)</p>
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<p>E-Infrastructure For Data And Computing Intensive Service</p>	<p>ISO</p>	<p>ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies ISO/TC 307 WG6 Use Cases ISO/TC 307 AG1 SBP Review Advisory Group ISO/TC 307 CAG1 Chairs Advisory Board ISO/TC 307 WG1 Foundational ISO/TC 307 JWG4 Security and Privacy ISO/TC 307 WG5 Governance ISO/TC 307 WG7 Interoperability ISO/TC 307 AG3 Digital Currencies</p>
<p>Sustainable Growth</p>		
<p>Smart and Sustainable Cities</p>	<p>ISO CEN ITU</p>	<p>ISO/TC 178 Lifts, escalators and moving walks ISO/TC 178/WG 4/6; CEN/TC 10 Lifts, escalators and moving walks CEN/TC 10/ WG 2; ITU-T Study Group 20 Internet of things (IoT) and smart cities and communities (SC&C)</p>
<p>Smart Grids And Smart Metering</p>	<p>CISPR IEEE IEC ISO/IEC</p>	<p>CISPR/CIS A/JWG 9: Rapid emission check of installations IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots, IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3 IEC SyC Smart Energy CAG, ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 AG6, CEN/CLC/ ETSI CG-SG ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41 Internet of things and digital twin</p>
<p>Robotics and autonomous systems</p>	<p>IEEE</p>	<p>IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots IEEE WG 1872.1 - Robot Task Representation IEEE WG 3140 - Semantic Map for Autonomous Robots Working Group IEEE WG 3107: Human-Robot Interaction Terminology IEEE WG 3108: Recommended Practice for Human-Robot Interaction Design of Human Subject Studies</p>

	IEEE	IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots IEEE WG 3140 - Semantic Map for Autonomous Robots Working Group IEEE WG 1872.1.1: Guide for the Practical Implementation of IEEE RAS Standard 1872.1 on Robotic Task Representation.
ICT environmental impact	IETF	NMRG
Intelligent Transport Systems	ISO	ISO/TC 204 Intelligent transport systems WG3 ITS geographic data ISO/TC 211 Geographic information JWG 11
	CEN	CEN/TC 278 Intelligent transport systems WG 7
Building Information Modelling	CEN	CEN/TC442/WG2/PT5
Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport	ITU	Q7/SG5
	CEN	CEN Ad Hoc Group Information sharing; Ad Hoc Group EU Circular Economy Terminology, Framework & Principles; Ad Hoc Group Extended producer responsibility; Ad Hoc Group Circular Business models; Ad Hoc Group EU Circular Economy Terminology, Framework & Principles; Ad Hoc Group Extended producer responsibility; Ad Hoc Group Circular business models
	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELC JTC 19 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG 2 Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and DLTs; CEN/CENELEC Standardisation Request Ad-hoc group (SRAHG) on Digital Product Passport

Innovation for Digital Single Market

<p>Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies</p>		<p>ISO</p> <p>ISO/TC 307 ISO/TC Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies AG 1 - Convenor AG1 Strategic Business Plan Review Advisor Group, ISO/TC 307/WG 1 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology - Foundations ISO/TC 307/AG 3 Digital Currencies ISO/TC307 WG3 Smart Contracts and DLT ISO/TC307 JWG4 Security and Privacy ISO/TC 307 WG5 Governance ISO/TC 307 WG6 Use Cases ISO/TC 307 WG7 Interoperability ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1 Archives/Records Management - Blockchain ISO/TC 68/AG 5 Digital Currencies, ISO/TC 68/SC 8/WG 3 Digital Token Identifier ISO/TC215 Liaison Medical Informatics</p> <p>ISO/IEC CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup CEN/CLC/JTC 19 "Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies" WG 01 "Decentralised identity management"</p> <p>ISO</p> <p>ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies ISO/TC 307 Convenor or WG6, and technical expert to WG1 Foundational, y, WG5 Governance, , AG3 Digital Currencies</p>
<p>Metaverse including Citiverse</p>		<p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 7 MPEG Coding for 3D Graphics and Haptics ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 2 MPEG Requirements</p> <p>ITU</p> <p>ITU Focus Group on Metaverse, Working Group 8 Accessibility and inclusion</p> <p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC1 Information Technology</p>
<p>Fin Tech and Reg Tech Standardisation</p>		<p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG5 - Identity and Privacy Management</p>
<p>Digitisation Of European Industry</p>		<p>CEN</p> <p>CEN442 WG9 and liasons with WG4 and WG2</p>

ANNEX 7 LIST OF NEW AND REVISED STANDARDS ADDRESSED BY THE FUNDED FELLOWSHIPS

ICT Area	MainSDO	Related Working Group or Technical Committee	Contributed to a new or a revised standard	Which revised or new standard?
Foundational Drivers				
Cybersecurity Network and Information Security	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG5 on Identity management and privacy technologies	Revised Standard	ISO/IEC 24760-1 about identity management terminology and concepts ISO/IEC 24760-2 about identity management architecture ISO/IEC 24760-3 about identity management practices ISO/IEC 24760-4, about identity management and credentials, authenticators and authentication ISO/IEC 29146 about access management amendment ISO/IEC 29184 about online privacy notices and consent
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification	Revised Standard	Some findings of this standard development have contributed to revision of other standards such as e.g. ISO/IEC 24787 and ISO/IEC 7816-11 via liaison comments.
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC17 WG11 Application of biometrics to cards and personal identification	New standard	ISO/IEC 17839-2, ISO/IEC 17839-1, ISO/IEC 17839-3.
	ISO/IEC	ISO JTC1 WG4; including ISO TC292 WG2	Revised Standard	ISO 27031's revision project and to secure my participation in all the dedicated meetings on one hand, but also, on the other hand ISO 27035-x projects meetings

ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 AhG2, AhG3 & WG4	Both new and revised	<p>ISO/IEC 27040:2024 IT - Security techniques — Storage security</p> <p>ISO/IEC 27402:2023 Cybersecurity — IoT security and privacy — Device baseline requirements</p> <p>ISO/IEC 27071:2023 Cybersecurity — Security recommendations for establishing trusted connections between devices and services</p> <p>ISO/IEC CD 27090 Cybersecurity — Artificial Intelligence — Guidance for addressing security threats and failures in artificial intelligence systems</p>
ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27 WG 2, "Cryptography and security mechanisms	New standard	a new standard and will be known as Rec. ITU-T X.508 ISO/IEC 9594-12, Key management and public-key infrastructure establishment and maintenance.
ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC SC27 WG2	New standard	Yes, I have contributed to the development of three different parts of a new standard, ISO/IEC 4922 Secure multiparty computation (-1, -2 and -3).
CEN/CENELEC	CEN CENELEC JTC 13 and working groups,	New standard	The Working Group 8 of CEN-CENELEC JTC 13 aims at producing CEN-CENELEC standard prEN 18031, which is currently in drafting. My participation as a member of this group to the effort of producing the standard, contributes to work of drafting the 3 harmonised standards.
CEN/CENELEC	CEN CENELEC JTC 13 and working groups, ETSI TC CYBER	New standard	producing CEN-CENELEC standard prEN 18031, which is currently in drafting.
O-RAN	O-RAN Alliance, WG11: Security Work Group, Security Testing Work Item	Revised Standard	All our efforts were directed to complete the current specification of network security tests. The current specification has not deployed all the tests of the security requirements and security controls developed by O-RAN Alliance, so the tests need to be specified in further versions of the specifications. The name of the revised standard is: "Security Tests Specification O-RAN.WG11.SecTestSpecs".

	ETSI	ETSI TC CYBER	New standard	Yes, I contributed to the development of a new standard TR 103 936 V1.1.1 (2024-01) Implementing Design practices to mitigate consumer IoT-enabled coercive control.
	ITU	ITU-T Study Group 17 Q11 and ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 6 WG 10	Revised Standard	ITU-T X.510
Data Economy	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC41	New standard	SC41 PWI16, SC41 PWI17, 21823-5, 27564.
E-privacy	CEN	ETSI ESI	New standard	Yes, the work on this project has directly influenced ETSI ESI to create a new standard relating to Relying Party access to personal data in the wallet.
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 3, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 37, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC 24745, CEN/ CNLC JTC 13	Revised Standard	The activities are in particular directly related to revision of 19792 and the development of a future (new) standard 27553-2. In addition the revision of 19989 is under discussion and might be initiated soon.
Key enablers and Security				
5G & beyond, 6G	ETSI	ETSI TC INT AFI WG	New standard	Yes, the development of ETSI TR 103 857: Generic Framework for E2E Federated GANA Knowledge Planes for AI-powered Closed-Loop Self-Adaptive Security Management & Control Across Multi-Domain 5G Networks
	ETSI	ITU-T SG11 and Focus Group on Testbeds Federations	New standard	BFxG-O-077-R1 Technical Report D1.1: Use cases for federated testbeds and business scenarios ITU-T Focus Group on Testbeds Federations (14-16 February 2024).
	IEEE	IEEE VTS AI in Wireless Communications Committee	New standard	IEEE P1948 Standard for AI-based Network Applications in 5G and beyond
	ISO	ISO TC211 WG6 Geographic Imagery	Revised Standard	an update of ISO 19123-2 that defines interoperable data structures for spatio-temporal Big Data

Big data, open data and public sector information	ISO/IEC	ISO IEC/JTC1/ SC32/WG3 Database languages	New standard	ISO 39075 GQL will come out in April of of 2024 in its first release.
Internet Of Things	IEC	IEC Systems Committee on Active Assisted Living, IEC Systems Committee on Smart Cities, ISO/IEC JTC 1 - Information technology, IEC TC 100 Audio, video and multimedia systems and equipment, IEC Systems committee on Communications Technologies and Architectures and JTC 1 SC41 IoT and Digital Twin.	New standard	Work on strategic standardisation plans in JTC1 and IEC TC100 will lead to NWIPs for technologies identified as priority in different subgroups. The chairing of ROLL (Routing Over Low Power and Lossy Networks) at the IETF led to the development of the following standard work: Supporting Asymmetric Links in Low Power Networks: AODV-RPL (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Root initiated routing state in RPL (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Controlling Secure Network Enrollment in RPL networks (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Mode of Operation extension (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track); Common Ancestor Objective Function and Parent Set Destination Oriented Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) Metric Container Extension (Document in progress proposed as Standard Track).
	IETF	IETF ROLL Working Group, IETF IoT-Directorate, IETF Routing-Directorate, IETF Gen-Area Review Team	New standard	

E-Identification and Trust Services	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17/WG11	New standard	<p>the development of the following standards:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ISO/IEC 17839-1 WD2 - Information technology — Biometric System-on-Card — Part 1: Core requirements. - ISO/IEC 17839-3 WD2 - Information technology — Biometric System-on-Card — Part 3: Logical information interchange mechanism. <p>This standard is a Technical Specification identified as WI=00224276 “Guidelines for the onboarding of user personal identification data within European Digital Identity Wallets”.</p> <p>The activity proposes an agenda for the future evolution of standards in the health information and AI domain to maximize the value of AI in healthcare and health research.</p> <p>There are ongoing discussions for revision of ISO/IEC 29115 which have progressed, and early discussions for potential additional new projects around digital identity.</p>
	CEN	CEN/TC 224/WG 20,	New standard	
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC SC37 WG3	Revised Standard	
	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27/WG 5, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 27, ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 17	Revised Standard	
Quantum Technologies	CEN/CENELEC	Cen Cenelec JTC 22, QuIC Standardisation Working Group	Both new and revised	<p>CEN-CENELEC JTC22, particularly WG4, aims to draft essential technical standards for quantum technologies, which are vital for creating a secure and interoperable quantum communication infrastructure across Europe. Continuing our work in this field is crucial to establish standards and ensure the secure integration of Quantum Communication Infrastructures (QCIs) within the EU.</p> <p>IEC 6xxxx Technical Report on Quantum Interconnect and Standardisation Roadmap</p>
	IEC	IEC SEG 14 on Quantum Technologies, IEC TC 86/JWG 9 - Optical functionality for electronic assemblies (Optical circuit boards), IEC TC86 / SC86B (Fibre optic interconnecting devices and passive components)	New standard	

Artificial intelligence	CEN/CENELEC	CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21/WG 1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and ISO-IEC/SC 42/AG 3 (AI Standardisation roadmapping)	New standard	At the SC 42 level: "AI maturity model" At the JTC 21 level: "Operational design domain for AI systems" and "AI trustworthiness framework"
	CEN/CENELEC	CNE/CLC/JTC21 project on "AI Conformity assessment" (WG2), project on "Data Governance and data quality for AI in the European context" (WG2), project on "Check List for AI Risks Management" (WG2) and project on "AI trustworthiness characterization" (WG4), AFNOR (ethics committee on AI), ISO/IEC SC 42 JTC1 WG3 on "AI trustworthiness", Others	New standard	Three projects are directed addressed to NWIP: CEN-CENELEC JTC21 WG4 TG2 editor: "AI-enhanced nudging" CEN-CENELEC JTC21 WG4 TG4 co-editor: "Competence Requirements for AI Ethicists Professionals" CEN-CENELEC JTC21 WG4 TG3 "AI trustworthiness Framework" that I animate as co-convenor of WG4

	CEN/CENELEC	Focus during the period will be on CEN/CENELEC JTC21 side, the intention is to continue my leadership role (Co-Convenor) of JTC21 WG1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and Head of the Belgian delegations to ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC. My additional target: co-lead the newly established Task Group on AI Cybersecurity within JTC21 WG1.	New standard	Two Preliminary Work Items (PWIs) were approved at the JTC21 plenary meeting in the week 12-16 February 2024. One PWi for contributions towards enhancement of ISO/IEC 27090 and another PWi to develop a home-grown European Standard on technical solutions to address AI specific vulnerabilities.
	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 / WG 3	New standard	Subject to the balloting process, the new work item proposal will lead to an ISO/IEC and CEN/CENELEC standard.
	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 WG 4 - Foundational and social aspects	New standard	PWi on “Competence Requirements for AI Ethicists Professionals” into a New Work Item Proposal (NWIP) to be submitted for national body voting.

	<p>CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>CEN/CLC/JTC 21 “Artificial Intelligence” (contributing to WG 1 “Strategic Advisory Group” and WG 3 “Engineering Aspects”), ISO/IEC/JTC 1/SC 42 “Artificial Intelligence”, WG 3 “Trustworthiness”, WG 5 “Computational approaches and computational characteristics”, ISO/TC 37 “Language and terminology”</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>Development of ISO/IEC TR 23281, ISO/IEC AWI 23282, ISO/IEC TS 6254, ISO/IEC 12792. Also incubating in CEN/CLC/JTC 21 NWIPs on datasets, on bias, on computer vision and on AI cybersecurity.</p>
	<p>CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>CEN/CLC/JTC 21 “Artificial Intelligence” WG 2-4 Operational, Engineering, Foundational and Societal aspects</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>Contributions to JTC21 WG1-4 relate to the Standardisation request of the European Commission on among others risk management systems for AI systems, on governance and quality of datasets used to build AI systems, on human oversight of AI systems and conformity assessment for AI systems.</p>

	<p>CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>CNE/CLC/JTC21 project on “AI Conformity assessment” (WG2), project on “ Data Governance and data quality for AI in the European context” (WG2), project on “ Check List for AI Risks Management “ (WG2) and project on “AI trustworthiness characterization” (WG4), AFNOR (ethics committee on AI), ISO/IEC SC 42 JTC1 WG3 on “AI trustworthiness”, “Ethics”</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>CEN-CENELEC JTC21 WG4 TG2 editor: "AI-enhanced nudging" , and contributor to TG3 “AI trustworthiness Framework” , and TG1 “Green and Sustainable AI”</p>
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	<p>CEN/CENELEC</p> <p>Focus during the period will be on the CEN/CENELEC JTC21 side. The intention is to continue my leadership role (Co-Convenor) of JTC21 WG1 (Strategic Advisory Group) and Head of the Belgian delegation to CEN/CENELEC JTC21. My additional target: continue co-leading the Task Group on Cybersecurity for AI Systems within JTC21 WG1 and involvement in the new JTC21 WG5 as soon as it becomes operational.</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>1. Initiate “parallel development” between ISO/IEC SC27 and CEN/CENELEC JTC21 of the technical report ISO/IEC 27090. 2. Initiate the drafting of a ‘homegrown’ European Standard (EN) addressing AI-specific vulnerabilities in response to the EC standardisation request. Proposed title: Cybersecurity specifications for AI Systems.</p>
	<p>ISO</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>ISO/IEC AWI TR 18988 "Artificial intelligence - Application of AI technologies in health informatics".</p>
	<p>ISO</p> <p>ISO/TC 46/SC 9/WG 18 – ISO/DIS 24138 – International Standard Content Code</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>ISO/CD 24138, the International Standard Content Code</p>
	<p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/IEC JTC1 SC42 WG3 (Trustworthiness)</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>ISO/IEC/SC/WG3 TS22443 - Artificial Intelligence - Guidance on addressing societal concerns and ethical considerations</p>

	Cross-SDO	EITCI SMART-PV-SESG (Smart Energy Standards Group hosted under EITCI Institute)	New standard	The action led to publishing advanced versions of the technical reference standards of the EITCI SESG: 1) in AI Smart PV systems definitions, concepts, architectures and use cases, and 2) in AI Smart PV technical specification of processes and devices.
	ETSI	ETSI SmartM2M (Machine-To-Machine) Communication Working Group and ETSI OCG (Operational Co-ordination Group) on Artificial Intelligence.	New standard	All activities are performed in tandem with the ongoing work related to the ETSI STF641 and STF628 aiming to develop standards related to the definition and adoption of interoperable Digital Twins architectures. Currently, a standard covering this domain does not exist.
Cloud computing	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC/JTC1/SC27 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection/WG1 Information security management systems	Revised Standard	The project was used to lead the development and revision of different standards. Mainly, we managed to cancel the working study (PWI) on the 27003 to start the revision project. Similarly, we moved to a CD stage on two of the other standards this is a great achievement for the development of the 27028 and 27017 standards.
Sustainable Growth				
Smart cities	ITU	ITU-T Study Group 20 Internet of things (IoT) and smart cities and communities (SC&C)	New standard	ITU-T Recommendation Y.4205 : Requirements and reference model of IoT-related crowdsourced systems; SG20/Q5 YSTR.P2P-CC Current state of P2P crowd charging platforms and corresponding market needs
Smart Grids And Smart Metering	IEC	IEC SyC Smart Energy JWG3, IEC SyC Smart Energy CAG	New standard	I contribute to the revision of an existing standard , IEC TR 63097 Smart Energy Roadmap as well as a to the development of a new standard IEC SRD 63460 Architecture and use-cases for EVs to provide grid-support function.

IEC	<p>CISPR/CIS A/JWG 9: Rapid emission check of installations. Other related standards are CISPR 37, CISPR 11 and CISPR 16-2-5. IEC TC82 and CENELEC TC219 of PLC are very interested as well.</p>	Both new and revised	Writing of the new CISPR 37 and in the maintenance of CISPR 11
IEEE	<p>IEEE SA P 1872.3 REMAR - Ontology for reasoning on multiple autonomous robots, IEEE SA P1872.2 Autonomous Robotics (AuR) Ontology Working Group</p>	New standard	<p>the IEEE P1872.3 standard, which is a logical extension to the IEEE 1872.2 and CORA ontology by defining additional ontologies appropriate for Autonomous Robotics (AuR).</p>

Robotics and autonomous systems	IEEE	IEEE WG 1872.3 - Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots; IEEE WG 1872.1 - Robot Task Representation ; IEEE WG 3140 - Semantic Map for Autonomous Robots Working Group ; IEEE WG 3107: Human-Robot Interaction Terminology ; IEEE WG 3108: Recommended Practice for Human-Robot Interaction Design of Human Subject Studies	New standard	The TWG on Robotics. The new IEEE RAS robotic standard WG 1872.3 is in good shape and is at its first year of work. Bi-weekly meetings are underway. Two workshops at the major IEEE robotic conference (ICRA, in 2023 and 2024) were approved which is excellent. I am honoured to be the chair of the WG, where European experts are very well represented in the group of voting members. Recently a new IEEE working group was formed, based on the 1872.1, to develop a guide for the application of the robot task representation (the new 1872.1.1), that I also am a member.
Ict environmental impact	IETF	NMRG	New standard	Shepherd of "Challenges and Opportunities in Management for Green Networking"
Intelligent Transport Systems	CEN	CEN/TC 278/WG 7 - ISO/TC 204/WG 3 - ISO/TC 211/JWG 11	New standard	CEN/TS 17268 "Intelligent transport systems - ITS spatial data - Data exchange on changes in road attributes" (ed. 2) CEN ISO/TS 22726-2 "Intelligent transport systems — Dynamic data and map database specification for connected and automated driving system applications — Part 2: Logical data model of dynamic data" ISO/TS 22726-1 "Intelligent transport systems — Dynamic data and map database specification for connected and automated driving system applications — Part 1: Architecture and logical data model for harmonization of static map data" (ed. 2)
Building Information Modelling	CEN	CEN/TC442/WG2	New standard	EN ISO 16757-5.

Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport	ITU	Q7/SG5	New standard	L.D4PI ITU-T work item and corresponding ETSI EE EEPS work item.
Innovation for Digital Single Market				
Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	ISO	<p>ISO/TC 307 ISO/TC 307/AG 1 - Convenor AG1 Strategic Business Plan Review Advisor Group, CEN/CLC/JTC 19/WG 01</p> <p>"Decentralised identity management", ISO/TC 307 - Technical Expert WG5 Governance, ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in JWG4 Security, privacy and identity for Blockchain, ISO/TC307 - Technical Expert in WG3 Smart Contracts and DLT ISO/TC 307 – Technical Expert in WG6 Use Cases ISO/TC 307/CAG 1 Convenor and ISO/TC215, Liaison Medical Informatics, CEN/CLC/JTC 19 "Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies"</p>	New standard	This work has provided a strategy for ISO/TC 307 which has already impacted the AWI projects being run within the TC.

	<p>ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup Reference standards: ISO/IEC 21000-19 Media Value Chain Ontology (MVCO), 21000- 19/AMD1 Audio Value Chain Ontology (AVCO), 21000-20 Contract Expression Language (CEL), 21000-21 Media Contract Ontology (MCO), ISO/IEC 21000- 23 Smart Contracts for Media</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>ISO/IEC 23000-23 Decentralised Media Rights Application Format currently at the Working Draft (WD) stage.</p>
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	<p>ISO</p> <p>ISO/TC 307/WG 1 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology - Foundations, ISO/TC 46/SC 11/JWG 1 Archives/Records Management - Blockchain, ISO/TC 307/AG 1 SBP Review Advisory Group, ISO/TC 307/AG 3 Digital Currencies, ISO/TC 68/AG 5 Digital Currencies, ISO/TC 68/SC 8/WG 3 Digital Token Identifier</p>	<p>New standard</p>	<p>New work item, Digital Currencies – Vocabulary (ISO/NP 24982) New work item on Digital Currencies – Taxonomy and Ontology.</p> <p>I contribute to the development of several blockchain standards to improve the representation of consumers' interests. These include the following standardisation items: ISO/PWI 23095: 27002 for Distributed Ledger Services ISO/PWI 12833: Re-identification and Privacy Vulnerabilities in Blockchain ISO/PWI 23042 Decentralized identity ISO/NP TS 23353: Auditing Guidelines for Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology ISO/DTR TR 6277 Data Flows ISO/AWI TR 24878 New and emerging Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technology Use Cases ISO/AWI 24946 Requirements and guidance for improving, preserving, and assessing the privacy capability of DLT systems ISO/PWI 24875 Secure smart contracts ISO/PWI 24876 Privacy considerations for trust anchors in DLT-based Identity Management</p>
	<p>ISO/IEC</p> <p>ISO/TC 307 Blockchain and distributed ledger technologies</p>	<p>New standard</p>	

Digital product passport	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies, WG 2 Environmental Sustainability for Blockchain and DLTs; CEN/CENELEC Standardisation Request Ad-hoc group (SRAHG) on Digital Product Passport	New standard	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Technical Report, Environmental sustainability classification methodology of consensus mechanisms of Blockchain and DLTs. 2. New work item proposal of technical specification: Environmental Sustainability Taxonomy of Blockchain and DLT's.
Digitisation Of European Industry	CEN	CEN442 WG9 and liasons with WG4 and WG2	New standard	the O4BSIM will be hopefully a technical specification presented at CEN442 WG9
Fin Tech and Reg Tech Standardisation	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG5 - Identity and Privacy Management	New standard	<p>ISO/IEC AWI 27566-1 – Age Assurance Systems – Part 1: Framework. This is likely to progress to CD Ballot in the Summer of 2024. We are aiming for publication in Spring 2025</p> <p>ISO/IEC AWI 27566-2 – Age Assurance Systems – Part 2: Benchmarks for Benchmarking Analysis. This is currently at Working Draft Stage and will be progressed through 2024 with likely publication in late 2025</p> <p>ISO/IEC PWI 27566-3 – Age Assurance Systems – Part 3: Interoperability, Technical Architecture and Guidelines for Use. This project is at preliminary work item stage, with a new project ballot likely to take place in May 2024. It is likely this document will work towards publication in 2027.</p>
Metaverse	ITU	ITU Focus Group on Metaverse, Working Group 8 Accessibility and inclusion	New standard	I am contributing to a new standard “ITU Commun User Profile” being developed in ITU IRG AVA.

	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 7 MPEG Coding for 3D Graphics and Haptics; ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 29/WG 2 MPEG Requirements	New standard	ISO/IEC 23090-5:2023 Visual volumetric video-based coding (V3C) and video-based point cloud compression (V-PCC) ISO/IEC 23090-9:2023 Geometry-based point cloud compression (G-PCC) - ISO/IEC AWI 23090-29 Video-based dynamic mesh coding (V-DMC)
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ANNEX 8 – LIST OF FUNDED EXPERTS WITH A KEY ROLE IN A WORKING GROUP OR A TECHNICAL COMMITTEE

ICT Area	First Name	Surname	Position	SDO	Concerned WG / TC
Foundational Drivers					
E-Identification and Trust Services	Raul	Sanchez-Reillo	Convener	CEN	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC17 co-convenor of CEN TC224 WG20
	Bringer	Julien	Co-Convener	ISO/IEC	co-convenor of ISO/TC 307/JWG 4
Data Economy	Antonio	Kung	Chair	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41/AG31 ISO/IEC JTC1/SC41/AG25 ISO/IEC JTC1/SC27/WG5 AhG advancing 27091
Cybersecurity Network And Information Security	François	Lorek	Convener	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1 SC27 WG4 and of AHG2 (IoT & Digital Twin related Cybersecurity & Privacy projects)
Key enablers and Security					
5G & beyond, 6G	Alexandru	Vulpe	Chair	IEEE	Working Group “Network Applications in 5G and beyond” within the IEEE Communications Society under approval

	Muslim	Elkotob	Chair	ETSI	Chairman ETSI TC INT AFI Autonomic Future Internet Vice Chairman ETSI TC INT Technical Committee (TC) Core Network and Interoperability Testing (INT) Vice Chairman ITU-T ITU-T Focus Group on Testbeds Federations for IMT-2020 and beyond (FG-TBFxG) SG11
Artificial Intelligence	Sebastian	Posth	Chair	ISO	ISO/TC 46/SC 9/WG 18, ISO/DIS 24138
	Lauriane	Aufrant	Convener	CEN/CENELEC	ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42 JWG 5 “Natural language processing”
	Mauro	Dragoni	Chair	ETSI	ETSI SmartM2M TC
	Enrico	Panai	Co-chair or co-convener	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 of WG4 “Foundational and societal aspects”
	Francisco	Medeiros-Filho	Co-chair or co-convener	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG1 Strategic Advisory Group CEN/CENELEC JTC21 WG5 Cybersecurity for AI Systems
	Patrick	Bezombes	Convener	CEN/CENELEC	Convener of the CEN-CENELEC/JTC 21/WG 1 (Strategic advisory group) Convener of the ISO-IEC/SC 42/AG 3 (AI Standardisation road mapping).

	Enrico Panai	Co-Convener	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 21 co-convenor of WG4 “Foundational and societal aspects”
	Agnieszka Rządowska	Convener	Cross-SDO	EITCI Smart Energy Standards Group (SESG)
	Adam Smith	Chair	CEN/CENELEC	ISO/IEC/JTC1/SC42/JWG2 - Testing of AI systems
Quantum Technologies	Homer Papadopoulos	Moderator	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC22 “Quantum Technologies” / WG4 Quantum Communication and QKD / Work Item (Technical Report): Quantum Networks Best Practices
	Jacak Witold	Chair	CEN/CENELEC	EITCI Quantum Standards Group (QSG)
	Richard Pitwon	Chair	IEC	Chair of IEC TC86/SC86B Chair of BSI GEL 86 Chair of BSI GEL 86/2
Internet of Things	Maria Ines Robles	Co-Chair	IETF	Co-chair of the Routing Over Low power and Lossy networks (ROLL) working group, Co-chair of IETF Internet of Things (IoT) Directorate
Innovation for Digital Single Market				
Blockchain And Distributed Ledger Technologies	Caroline Thomas	Convener	ISO	Standards created in my Convener role of in ISO/TC 307 WG6 Use Cases
	Paull Ferris	Convener	ISO	ISO/TC 307/AG 1 SBP Review Advisory Group

	Panos	Kudumakis	Chair	ISO/IEC	ISO/IEC JTC1/SC29/WG03 MPEG Systems Smart Contracts for Media Subgroup
Metaverse	Pilar	Orero	Co-Chair	ITU	ITU FG MetaVerse WG8 Accessibility and Inclusion
	Marius	Preda	Chair	ISO/IEC	Convener of ISO/IEC JTC 1 SC 29 / WG 7 MPEG 3DGH
Building Information Modelling	Pierre-François	Jullien	Convener	CEN	AFNOR CN PPBIM/GE 2
Circular Economy Including Digital Product Passport	Leandro	Navarro	Moderator	ITU	ITU-T co-editor of this work item and coordination role as co-rapporteur of ITU-T Q7/SG5
	Suarez	Belen	Convener	CEN/CENELEC	CEN/CENELEC JTC 19 working group WG2 on Environmental Sustainability on Blockchain and Distributed Ledger Technologies
ICT environmental impact	François	Jérôme	Co-Chair	IETF	IETF NMRG
Intelligent Transport Systems	Loïc	Blaive	Convener	CEN	CEN/TC 278 Intelligent Transport systems /WG 7 "ITS spatial data"
Robotics and autonomous systems	Paulo	Gonçalves	Chair	IEEE	IEEE WG 1872.3 – Standard for Ontology Reasoning on Multiple Robots.
Smart Grids and Smart Metering	Olivier	Genest	Co-chair or co-convener	IEC	Co-convener of IEC SyC JWG3 "Smart Energy Roadmap"